

VALKYRIES

D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation

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1. Executive Summary

This document **D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation** describes the effectiveness of the VALKYRIES outcomes according to the validation and evaluation methodology (D7.1). This deliverable includes all the activities related to testing the components, modules, interfaces, procedures, etc., reference integrated as well as their interoperability, normalization, and harmonization to support first aid responses on disaster scenarios. This covers the evaluation of the whole VALKYRIES reference architecture, with integration tests and system validations.

Functional, modular, inter-modular, scalability and security tests were executed on the testbed developed and integrated in the adapted virtual labs and testbeds (T7.1). The validation and evaluation of integrations for use case demonstration and their outcomes will be performed, including a broad study based on the expectations and null/alternative hypothesis, and the impact of the massive cross-border demonstrations in both the attending stakeholders and the expected operational and collaborative enhancements. The latter will also assess the effect of the demonstration outcomes bearing in mind the opinions of experts.

The following summarises the main contributions of D7.3:

- Harmonisations to be verified by Inspection, analysis, test, and demonstration.
- The scope of the harmonization opportunities and justification.
- **System Validation definition**
- Criteria for assessing compliance based on effectiveness measures (EM), performance measures (MR) and parameters or key performance indicators (KPIs).

The results achieved in each verification test, the quality of the results and the validation questionnaires are provided in each UC Report.

Changes from previous version A0 of this document have been highlighted in yellow according to the general project review consolidated report for easy identification.

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

Verification and validation are essential quality assurance activities. Both processes are designed to ensure that a product meets its intended requirements and specifications. The verification process focuses on checking whether the product has been created correctly according to its specified requirements, design and standards. It examines the internal consistency and adherence of the product to predefined guidelines. On the other hand, validation deals with assessing whether the right product has been produced, i.e., whether it fulfils the end users' needs and intended use. It evaluates the external behaviour and the usefulness of the product in the real world.

System validation and evaluation are crucial phases in the product development lifecycle, ensuring that the final product meets end user needs, and performs reliably in real-world scenarios.

The purpose of this deliverable is to document activities and outcomes related to the verification and validation processes of the identified harmonization opportunities, including the specified initial requirements. The implementation of these processes follows the definitions, guidelines and methodology defined within the framework of task 7.1 [D7.1]. The verification process includes testing the components, different modules, interfaces, procedures, etc., along with their integrated references, to ensure interoperability and harmonization, supporting the first aid responses in disaster scenarios. The validation and evaluation of integrated VALKYRIES solution for use case demonstrations are performed, including a comprehensive study based on end users' expectations, as well as the impact of the massive cross-border demonstrations on both attending stakeholders and expected operational collaborative enhancements. The effectiveness of the demonstration outcomes is assessed based on the elicitation of experts' and stakeholders' opinions through questionnaires. Validation results will be documented in the Use Cases reports.

3.1. Verification of the harmonisation opportunities

According to the methodology D7.1 [7], the term verification means the process of providing objective evidence that the system, software or hardware and its associated products conform to requirements (e.g., for correctness, completeness, consistency and accuracy) for all life cycle activities during each life cycle process (acquisition, supply, development, operation and maintenance).

The aim of the verification process is to confirm that a system or its elements meet the specified design requirements. Throughout every level of the development process, this process serves as a form of quality control. It enables the possibility to create systems that satisfy both design and end user's requirements. Each harmonization opportunity is associated with requirements defined in D2.8 in chapter 4. The verification process of the opportunities includes the implementation of identified harmonization opportunities and adherence to the defined requirements. In that way, during the verification process of the opportunity, the related system requirements are also evaluated and verified.

Qualification methods for verification D7.1 in chapter 7.3.2 that are used within the framework of Task 7.4. Evaluation and Validation, are presented herein:

3.1.1. Verification by Inspection

Inspection is the examination of the product or system using the basic senses, so they are physically examined based on their required physical characteristics and the control mechanisms they are supposed to present. Similarly, in the case of a software system, testers must check that its user interface is as required, presenting all the fields and data entry buttons it is supposed to have, etc.

In the context of VALKYRIES, a thorough documentary inspection of the Project results will be carried out throughout its product life cycle, in which the evaluators will be able to constantly provide information, assessments and, when required, the approval of the Consortium's decisions. These documentary inspections shall be complemented by a direct human inspection of the capabilities delivered, mainly targeting user interfaces and related user-friendly information sources.

Regarding the inspection of codes and software, human evaluation measures will be supported by third-party instruments deployed in the development environment and on the test beds (Virtual Laboratory), which will automatically facilitate the discovery of inconsistencies, errors, missing fields, etc.

3.1.2. Verification by Test

Test is technically the most accurate and controlled process of verifying a capability. Based on this, evaluators can confirm that a functionality operates as expected contextualized in a series of specifications, pre-conditions, and post-condition expectations. Tests are typically repeated by alternating different configuration parameters and input data, tracing step by step their feed flow and observable intermediate results. VALKYRIES preliminarily considers the execution of at least four types of tests:

- **Unit tests** - Verifications supported by specific software that allows to automate that the execution of functionalities of the system to be evaluated result in the expected results previously defined.
- **Integration test** - Verifications to be carried out in the field of software development once the unit tests have been approved, evaluating that all the unitary elements that make up the software work together correctly operating in a group.
- **Reliability test** - Tests focused on evaluating the reliability of the functions to be verified, given the environmental conditions, and for a certain time.
- **Security test** - Tests aimed at evaluating the level of vulnerability and risk in the different attack surfaces present in the functionalities to be verified.

3.1.3. Verification by Analysis

Validation by Analysis is applied in place of, or in addition to, test and demo checks to verify compliance with specification harmonization opportunities. Selected techniques may include systems engineering analysis, statistics and qualitative analysis, computer analysis and simulations; typically relying on benchmarks and collections of reference results. It is applied in the verification actions in which the VALKYRIES Consortium determines that:

- Rigorous and accurate analysis is possible.
- Test ratings are neither feasible nor profitable.
- Similarity (acceptance by previously accepted similar results) is not applicable.

- Inspection Verification is not adequate

3.1.4. Verification by Demonstration

Demonstration verifies the operation of the system or a part of the system, based on an observable functional operation that does not require the use of instrumentation, special test equipment or subsequent analysis. Demo verification means that the product or system being evaluated behaves as it should. Therefore, the person(s), appointed to technically verify the solutions, can follow the functional harmonisation opportunities described and verify that the evaluation object behaves as specified. In the case of software solutions, testers often enter the information just as users will, making sure the software performs the actions it is supposed to and checking that their reports are correct [5].

3.1.5. Verification by feed-back questionnaire for the first responders participating in UCs execution

The questionnaire was developed by VALKYRIES partners in the framework of D7.1 [5]. The role of this questionnaire is to receive feedback evaluation from the first responders with respect to the demonstrated technological tools, operative procedures and E&T materials to improve collaboration among the first responders from different nations and different institutions in case of cross-border MCI. The questions included in the feedback questionnaire cover a broad spectrum of topics related to the functionality of SIGRUN, applicability and usefulness of the first responders' organisations, etc. Besides, there are questions measuring to what extent the SIGRUN solution facilitates the information sharing between different agencies involved in a cross-border MCI and the level of satisfaction with the functionalities of the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution. Furthermore, the questionnaires measure the perceptions of the first responders regarding the usefulness of the training with the Joint Multinational Training Kit for first responders, as well as the CIMIC course for completion of their tasks in Multi casualty Incidents and supports the process of identification of the level of acceptance of the suggested harmonisation opportunities in WP6. It measures also the level of satisfaction with the demonstrated and tested courses. Finally, the questionnaire measures the level of acceptance of the WP5 harmonisation opportunities and triage procedures. The results from the feedback survey among first responders are presented as an annex in the UCs reports.

Sections 5, 6, and 7 includes the set of VALKYRIES harmonisation opportunities relevant to WP4, WP5 and WP6 respectively, to be verified and validated.

3.1.6. Valkyries Approach for harmonization Opportunities Verification

The verification process has focused on the opportunities for WP4, WP5 and WP6 described in D4.4 [2].

The technological opportunities from WP4 are verified into the SIGRUN platform acting as a federated system of various technological solutions provided by the Valkyries partners. Several verifications of each integration and unit tests have been carried out for each UC prior to the execution of the exercise. Each UC has created its own structure with a specific URL and API and the static emergency data (organisations, assets) have been loaded. The tests verified that the integration of the Command-and-Control tools (iSafety and GLOBAL COP) and the Applications for digitalizing triage process works according to the architecture model defined in the project 93Consortium VALKYRIES. Deliverable D2.8, "Architecture Design Document". 2022. and the

scenario defined for each UC (agencies, missions created, resources and personnel assigned) was executed, adjusting the data model for each scenario.

In the execution of unit tests, integration tests and demonstrations, project-specific requirements have been verified. Only tests or demonstrations requiring data or KPIs from a real execution environment have been executed during the UC.

For the verifications and demonstrations, only the necessary adaptations have been developed on SIGRUN and on the applications to be able to verify the tests and demonstrations, but the SIGRUN reference model is much broader as described in D2.8 [3].

Regarding WP5 approach, in relation to the WP5 harmonisation opportunities and the related specific enablers described in deliverable D5.4 [7], a verification process is carried out in 2 phases:

A) PRELIMINARY TESTING: Designed and conducted to evaluate and verify that the proposed enabler works as designed and, in the expert's judgement, is suitable to advance the opportunity to which it relates. Enables the detection and correction of deviations or errors and the improvement of performance. Regarding the WP5 enablers, several types of preliminary tests have been carried out:

1. **Cognitive walkthrough test** is an evaluation method in which one or more experts perform a series of tasks and ask a set of questions from the user's perspective. Based on the scenarios and tasks that users are expected to perform, the evaluator carries them out by assuming the role of the user. During the execution of this technique, the tasks to be performed by the user are analysed and the problem-solving process of each stage of the interaction process is simulated. Based on the analysis, an evaluation is carried out with a view to implementing the solutions to the above errors/areas of improvement in the prototype. (Wharton C, Rieman J, Lewis C, Polson P. The Cognitive Walkthrough: A practitioner's guide. 1994. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:53925427>)
2. **Specific validation tests:**
 - a. **In the context of specific actions:** The group to be used as the sample for the preliminary test is identified and an information activity (if it does not involve the acquisition and/or use of specific tools or skills) or training activity (if it does) is carried out on that group. At the end of the activity, the relevant information is obtained from the group and test results are analysed.
 - b. **In the context of MCI drills prior to UCs:** An MCI exercise is carried out with the participation of experts (first responders, disaster managers, technologists, etc.) capable of assuming the different roles defined in the exercise (first responders, C2, etc.), who will handle the tools necessary to carry out the exercise and enable the evaluation of the specific enabler. At the end of the exercise, relevant feedback is obtained from the group of participating experts to evaluate the enabler.

B) DEMONSTRATIONS: In the later phases of the project, the VALKYRIES use cases (UCs) will present to the target audiences the results of the certification, regulation, standardisation and harmonisation WP5 activities, as well as the improvement potential derived from the combination of solutions on the SIGRUN platform. In this context, a set of selected procedures and solutions will be harmonised and deployed in the context of cross-border MCIs based on UCs, where end-users and Consortium experts, supported by local partner response teams, will demonstrate the results. Proposals related to WP5 will primarily be brought to the demonstration scenarios of UCs 1, 2 and 3, and will basically consist of:

- 1. In the context of specific actions:** Training and role-playing activities, on the operational procedures and solutions specifically proposed by VALKYRIES Project for the demonstration, are included in the days of the UCs immediately prior to the exercise itself. These activities are essential for the adequate performance of first responders, C2 managers, etc. during the exercise. At the end of these activities, feedback is obtained from the participants for evaluation.
- 2. In the context of the UCs drills:** In the UCs, a verification of the WP5 related enablers will be performed. The demonstration sometimes takes place in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform. Due to the methodological approach, the demonstration will normally require the development, in parallel or successively, of an exercise carried out in the usual way and another exercise carried out with the new operational procedures and/or solutions proposed by VALKYRIES. During and/or after the exercise, relevant information will be gathered to carry out the proposed demonstrations.

A common template has been used for all verifications and is included in Annex B. In the template and for each test is included the description of the test, the traceability of the requirements and Valkyries objectives and the integration tests reported in D7.4 [6].

In the case of WP6 the technological opportunities have been verified in the same way as WP4 and the rest of the opportunities have been verified via questionnaire as the rest of WP5 opportunities.

A detailed description of the tools and harmonization opportunities is included in Annex F - Harmonization Opportunities chapter. A matrix has also been included indicating which opportunities have been verified in each UC and the technological tools used for each opportunity.

3.2. System Validation

As stated in D7.1 [5], validation takes place during the trial-exercise conduct and is implemented concurrently as data collection runs in parallel with the execution of the UCs. The preparation of the data collection means has taken place during the planning phase of the trial exercise, thus confirming that the evaluation runs throughout the lifetime of the exercise. In the context of the VALKYRIES, validation is carried out by the end users (first responders and disaster managers) in two steps:

- 1. Validation of individual solutions, used by the end users.**

2. Overall validation of the VALKYRIES consolidated system (Such validation is described deeper in 93Consortium VALKYRIES. Deliverable D7.4. “Reference Integration and Lessons Learned Report”)

However, validation results will be documented in the respective Deliverables of the Use Cases.

3.3. Requirements compliance matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T7.4_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	D7.3	RECOMMENDED	Achieved (This document contains tests and demonstration definitions)
REQ_BASE_T7.4_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	D7.3	REQUIRED	Achieved (Tests for validation and evaluation are described in this document)
REQ_COM_T7.4_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	D7.4 D7.5 D7.6 D7.7 D7.8	OPTIONAL	Achieved (Several previous tests have been executed prior final pilot. Reported in UC reports and D7.4)
REQ_COM_T7.4_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5 D7.6 D7.7 D7.8	RECOMMENDED	Achieved (Evaluation of the drills were done and included in UC reports)
REQ_COM_T7.4_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	D7.3 D7.5 D7.6 D7.7 D7.8	RECOMMENDED	Achieved (C&C application has been tested in D7.3 and UC reports)
REQ_COM_T7.4_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	NA	OPTIONAL	Not implemented. VCMS out of the scope of the selected opportunities
REQ_COM_T7.4_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5 D7.6 D7.7 D7.8	RECOMMENDED	Achieved (Agile communication demonstrated in UCs. Results will be part of UC reports)
REQ_COM_T7.4_6	P2	VALK-OBJ-9	D7.5 D7.6 D7.7 D7.8	RECOMMENDED	Achieved (UCs have evaluated VALKYRIES opportunities and execution of the drill from a previous action plan described and reported as well in the UC reports)

Table 1 - Requirements compliance matrix T7.4

4. WP4 - Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses harmonization opportunities

4.1. CO.WP4.42: Reduce Voice Communication

Reducing telephone communication and automating emergency-related processes can be feasible with today's technologies and the implementation provided by Valkyries. In the scope of the project SIGRUN platform implements this functionality in a feasible way as it is described in [1].

It's quite clear that the command-and-control applications must improve their interoperability so that thirty-part applications can share the information [1] and this is a feature that we have implemented in mostly of the UC using SIGRUN with a Command-and-Control Application and developing the necessary features to share information.

For the current implementation of the harmonization in the UC described in D4.4 [2] we have implemented the reference model of SIGRUN and has tested and demonstrated in the UC (UC#1, UC#2, UC#3).

The main goal of this opportunity is that has been tested along all the UC in different scenarios and different implementations within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform in a harmonized way.

For this opportunity, two verification methods have been used, verification by test and verification by demonstration.

Below is a description of the verifications carried out.

4.1.1. Verification by Test

This section includes the unit tests performed to verify the integration with the SIGRUN platform that implements the opportunity related to the reduction of voice communication and manual work in an emergency. All these tests are necessary to guarantee the interoperability of the tools with the SIGRUN platform and have been verified prior to each execution of each UC. Each UC has been executed in a different infrastructure (URL and API specific) with its own static data (agencies, assets, etc.) and a verification of this environment has been carried out prior to the exercise. The current applications have been adapted according to the Reference Model of SIGRUN and in this section we include the unit tests and integration tests performed.

In addition to the unit tests performed to validate the integrations, specific tests for project requirements (e.g., the requirement concerning real-time information REQ_COM_T5.3.1) are included.

4.1.1.1. CO-WP4-42-T01- Reduce Voice Communication

Description: This test consists of verifying and validating that the data created digitally from the system applications is shared through SIGRUN. The information shared is related to incident, Tasks, Assets Assignment to Tasks and Assets Geo localization) and is accessible to the rest of the Command-and-Control applications

In addition, the following functional requirements shall be subject to validation during the execution of the test itself.

- The Command, Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR) platform SHALL run on different operating systems and any type of device.
- First Aid Vehicles data SHALL be displayed in a dashboard with its status, positions, ETA, etc.
- System MUST allow for data originated by one country to be classified, by the originator, as shareable or not shareable.
- The Command-and-Control Application developed on the SIGRUN platform MAY communicate over third Command and Control Applications
- All crucial data related with communications between systems through SIGRUN are logged and recorded using the blockchain technologies for audit, transparency and GDPR guidelines

The test is executed in the URL/API specified for each UC where the SIGRUN platform is deployed. A Command-and-Control tool (iSafety) connected to the SIGRUN platform is available. In some use cases (UC#1) the Command-and-Control tool of one of the countries has been simulated and, in some UCs, (UC#2 and UC#3) iSafety has been used with own data and Country Agencies on both sides. A GLOBAL COP has been deployed for each country at the command posts of each country. These tests were carried out prior to the day of the exercise.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T4.3_2, REQ_COM_T4.3_10
REQ_COM_T4.3_19, REQ_COM_T4.3_22

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5; VALK -OBJ-6; VALK -OBJ-7

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-T01- Reduce Voice Communication
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP4.42
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	<p>1. Incident creation. Shared information about incident:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Incident id -Geolocation of the incident -Type of incident (Fire, Traffic accident, Earthquake...) -Time of the incident -Geolocation <p>2. Task creation. Shared information about tasks (missions)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Task id - Incident id to which the task belongs -Type of task (Traffic cut, Medical Support, Control...) -Task Status <p>3. Assets updated. Shared information about asset status and location:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Asset id

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-T01- Reduce Voice Communication
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary and secondary status - Geolocation - Task assigned
Pre-processing/Analysis	The information related to incident is created using iSafety and shared through VALKYRIES to the Command-and-Control Centre applications.
Premises and limitations	<p>Connectivity between applications is necessary. For this test, 4G has been used. Connectivity between the terminals, workstations where is deployed iSafety and the SIGRUN platform has been verified before testing.</p> <p>Static data is created in SIGRUN Platform before the test (Organizations, Assets) for each country.</p> <p>Incident/ Task and Asset is created by a user with emergency service operator role. This operator has all information to create the incident, task and associate the Asset to the task.</p> <p>GLOBAL COP is web and accessible from tablets and workstations connected to SIGRUN (Multiplatform)</p> <p>SIGRUN users have been configured according to the permissions required to view the data that can be shared by each Agency.</p> <p>Assets geolocation is simulated using HTL or simulation tools connected to SIGRUN.</p> <p>Communication data and meta-data logged properly in SIGRUN blockchain module</p> <p>Tests are performed in SIGRUN deployment provided for each UC (URL and API)</p>
Security and Privacy Considerations	<p>No personal data will be used in these tests</p> <p>Only the permissions and users necessary for the test will be enabled.</p>
Brief Description of the Test	<p>STEPS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. An operator using iSafety, creates a new incident, specifying type of the incident, location and a short description. When operator click on Save Button to create the incident in iSafety, this information is sent to SIGRUN. Then, this incident is created in SIGRUN and this information is showed on Global COP web portal, and system applications can read this incident information from SIGRUN. 2. On a second step, Emergency service operator, using iSafety, create a new task, specifying type of the task and a short description. When operator click on Save

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-T01- Reduce Voice Communication
	<p>Button to create the task in iSafety, this information is sent to SIGRUN.</p> <p>Then, this incident is created in SIGRUN and this information is showed on Global COP web portal.</p> <p>3. On a third step, Emergency service operator, using iSafety, assign several assets to task. Then operator changes the status of the assets when they are on its way, or when they have arrived at the location of the incident.</p> <p>With HTL application, the location of the routes that the vehicles travel, from the moment they leave the origin site until they arrive at the incident site, is simulated.</p> <p>In all these cases, this information is sent from iSafety to SIGRUN.</p> <p>Then, this assets information is in SIGRUN, and this information is showed on Global COP web portal, and in system applications can read this incident information from SIGRUN.</p> <p>The GLOBAL COP information is displayed both on laptops that have access to the URL and on tablets provided for first responders (multi-platform).</p> <p>GLOBAL COP information is displayed at the command posts in each country and information is shared for incident management between countries.</p> <p>ALL DATA AND METADATA are encrypted and logged in a secure blockchain network (for historical analysis or any other legal future purpose)</p>

Table 2 - Associated tests CO.WP4.42-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-T01	Harmonisation description: The system MUST be able to generate, and updated information related to the incident creation
	<p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incident reported in SIGRUN - Task reported in SIGRUN - Asset assignment to task in incident is reported in SIGRUN - Asset status is reported in SIGRUN - Asset location is reported in SIGRUN - GLOBAL COP information accessible through different devices - GLOBAL COP information accessible in different countries <p>MR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - iSafety application updates data in SIGRUN - System applications can read data from SIGRUN from both countries - HTL application updates data in SIGRUN - GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in several devices (laptops, tablets) - GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in both countries

	- DATA AND METADATA logging is visualized on secured blockchain networks visible by authorized users
	KPI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KPI 1: Information about the incident available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI 2: information about the task available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI 3: Information about assets localization available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI 4. Information about assets associated to tasks available in SIGRUN. YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI 5. Information related to Incident/tasks/assets in GLOBAL COP is available through different devices. YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI6. KPI 5. Information about Incident/tasks/Assets in GLOBAL COP is available in both countries. YES/NO (Available = success)
	Verification: Test A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (information available YES and time elapsed 100% success) B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed (Information available YES and time elapsed: 50%). C: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded

Table 3 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.42-T01

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.1.1.2. CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication

Description: This test consists of verifying and validating that the data created digitally from the system applications is shared through SIGRUN (Digital Information Related to triage Process) and is accessible to the rest of the Command-and-Control applications that have the necessary permissions to view this information in a cross- border situation.

In addition, the following functional requirements shall be subject to validation during the execution of the test itself.

- The Command, Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR) platform SHALL run on different operating systems and any type of device.
- System MUST allow for data originated by one country to be classified, by the originator, as shareable or not shareable.
- Applications for digitalizing triage process MAY be able to communicate with Command-and-Control application supporting first responders
- System MUST allow for data originated by one country to be classified, by the originator, as shareable or not shareable.
- It SHALL communicated the data from the VCMS to Command-and-Control Application.
- The wearable devices MUST be able to send the acquired data to the platform.

- All relevant data and metadata exchanged with federated systems on SIGRUN will be encrypted and logged in secure blockchain network

The test is run on the URL/API specified for each CU, which is where the SIGRUN platform is deployed. Applications for digitalizing triage process can connect to the SIGRUN platform, which has been deployed on several terminals for each country. A GLOBAL COP is deployed in each country with the corresponding triage data that can be shared connected to SIGRUN.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T4.3_2, REQ_COM_T4.3_22, REQ_COM_T4.4_10, REQ_COM_T4.4_11, REQ_COM_T4.5.2.

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5; VALK -OBJ-6; VALK -OBJ-7, VALK -OBJ-8, VALK -OBJ-9

Associated test

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP4.42
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information related to victims: -Age Group (Adult, Child, Elder) -Gender (Male/Female) -Assistance Status (Waiting for assistance, waiting for evacuation, Evacuated, In destination) -Triage status (AT, ET) -Triage classification -Main Pathology -Transport -Staff reporting information
Pre-processing/Analysis	The information related to victims' status and location is shared through VALKYRIES to the Command-and-Control Centre applications from different countries
Premises and limitations	Connectivity between applications is necessary. For this test, 4G has been used. Connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform has been verified before testing. The terminals have been previously configured with the associated users. The vehicles and hospital have been assigned and have not been integrated with the command-and-control tool. Static data of Agencies, staff, assets from each country have been previously created in SIGRUN and have been to be consistent and correct.

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication
	Tests are performed in SIGRUN deployment provided for each UC.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be used in these tests Only the permissions and users necessary for the test will be enabled.
Brief Description of the Test	To carry out the tests, several mobile terminals will be provided in both countries. These terminals will be connected to SIGRUN to send data using the 4G network. It will be verified that the data of both the victims and the incident are transmitted in real time in SIGRUN in both countries and that they are accessible to the rest of the applications connected to the platform. It will be verified from the GLOBAL COP in both countries monitoring that the data is received correctly into SIGRUN. We will verify that the data is correct, and that the information sent is useful for the management of the incident with the First Responders. GLOBAL COP is web and accessible from tablets and workstations connected to SIGRUN (Multiplatform) SIGRUN users have been configured according to the permissions required to view the data that can be shared by each Agency. FEDERATED SYSTEMS will be recognized by SIGRUN's internal workflows and procedures (defined in WP5 D5.3 and by their permission to log data in secured defined blockchain network

Table 4 - Associated tests CO.WP4.42-T02

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-T02	Harmonisation description: The system MUST be able to generate and updated information related to the incident creation and victims
	EM: - Victims registration in SIGRUN - Victims status time update in SIGRUN - Victims triage data update in SIGRUN - GLOBAL COP information accessible through different devices - GLOBAL COP information accessible in different countries
	MR: - System applications updates incident data in SIGRUN - Command and control systems read data from SIGRUN - GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in several devices (laptops, tablets) - GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in both countries
	KPI: - KPI 1: Victim Registration available: YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI 2: Victim status time update (Triage STATUS) available: YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI 3. Victims triage data update (Triage STATUS) available: YES/NO (Available = success)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KPI 4. Information related Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available through different devices. YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI 5. Information about Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available in both countries. YES/NO (Available = success)
	<p>Verification: Test</p> <p>A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (information available YES and time elapsed 100% success)</p> <p>B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed (Information available YES and time elapsed: 50%).</p> <p>C: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded (Information available NO and time elapsed: <25%).</p>

Table 5 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.42-T02

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.1.1.3. CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication

Description: The test consists of verifying that the information update from SIGRUN is updated in real time in the Platform and the information is updated according to the central Database.

The test is executed in the URL/API specified for each UC where the SIGRUN platform is deployed. A Command-and-Control tool (iSafety) connected to the SIGRUN platform is available. A GLOBAL COP has been deployed for each country at the command posts of each country. These tests were carried out on to the day of the exercise while the demonstration is running.

To verify this requirement, we analysed the time of data creation from the iSafety Command and Control tool and verified the date of insertion in the centralised SIGRUN database.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T4.3.1.

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-5; VALK -OBJ-6

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP4.42
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	<p>1. Incident creation. Shared information about incident:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Incident id -Geolocation of the incident -Type of incident (Fire, Traffic accident, Earthquake...)

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Time of the incident -Geolocation 2. Task creation. Shared information about tasks (missions) -Task id - Incident id to which the task belongs -Type of task (Traffic cut, Medical Support, Control...) -Task Status 3. Assets updated. Shared information about asset status and location: - Asset id - Primary and secondary status - Geolocation - Task assigned
Pre-processing/Analysis	The information related to victims' status and incident location is created and shared through VALKYRIES to the Command Centres applications.
Premises and limitations	<p>Connectivity between applications is necessary. For this test, 4G has been used. Connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform has been verified before testing.</p> <p>Static data of Agencies, staff, assets have been previously created in SIGRUN and have been to be consistent and correct.</p> <p>Network latency has an impact on the measurements. No additional mechanisms have been used to improve this time. Conventional 4G networks have been used. The aim is to verify with a standard network under normal conditions.</p> <p>Incident/ Task and Asset is created by a user with emergency service operator role. This operator has all information to create the incident, task and associate the Asset to the task.</p> <p>GLOBAL COP is web and accessible from tablets and workstations connected to SIGRUN.</p> <p>SIGRUN users have been configured according to the permissions required to view the data that can be shared by each Agency.</p> <p>Tests are performed in SIGRUN deployment provided for each UC (URL and API).</p> <p>DATA AND METADATA are stored properly in SIGRUN Blockchain module.</p>
Security and Privacy Considerations	<p>No personal data will be used in these tests</p> <p>Only the permissions and users necessary for the test will be enabled.</p>

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication
Brief Description of the Test	<p>STEPS</p> <p>4. An operator using iSafety, creates a new incident, specifying type of the incident, location and a short description. When operator click on Save Button to create the incident in iSafety, this information is sent to SIGRUN. Then, this incident is created in SIGRUN and this information is showed on Global COP web portal, and system applications can read this incident information from SIGRUN.</p> <p>5. On a second step, Emergency service operator, using iSafety, create a new task, specifying type of the task and a short description. When operator click on Save Button to create the task in iSafety, this information is sent to SIGRUN. Then, this incident is created in SIGRUN and this information is showed on Global COP web portal.</p> <p>6. On a third step, Emergency service operator, using iSafety, assign several assets to task. Then operator changes the status of the assets when they are on its way, or when they have arrived at the location of the incident. With HTL application, the location of the routes that the vehicles travel, from the moment they leave the origin site until they arrive at the incident site, is simulated.</p> <p>In all these cases, this information is sent from iSafety to SIGRUN. Information is visualized in GLOBAL COP. This test is executed during the UC.</p>

Table 6 - Associated tests CO.WP4.42-T03

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-T01	<p>Harmonisation description: The system MUST be able to generate, and updated information related to the incident creation and victims in a centralized system in real time</p> <p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incident reported in SIGRUN (< than 60 s) - Task Registration in SIGRUN (< than 60 s) - Assets registration in SIGRUN (< than 60 s) - Assets update in SIGRUN (< than 60 s) <p>MR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - System applications update data in SIGRUN - Command and control systems read data from SIGRUN <p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KPI 1: Time elapsed (since Incident is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o < 60 sec 100% success o Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success○ > 120 sec 0% success- KPI 2: Time elapsed (since task is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ < 60 sec 100% success○ Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success○ Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success○ > 120 sec 0% success- KPI 3: Time elapsed (since asset is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ < 60 sec 100% success○ Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success○ Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success○ > 120 sec 0% success- KPI 4: Time elapsed (since asset is updated in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ < 60 sec 100% success○ Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success○ Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success○ > 120 sec 0% success
	<p>Verification: Test</p> <p>A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (information available YES and time elapsed 100% success)</p> <p>B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed (Information available YES and time elapsed: 50%).</p> <p>C: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded (Information available NO and time elapsed: <25%).</p>

Table 7 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.42-T03

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.1.2. Verification by Demonstration

4.1.2.1. CO-WP4-42-D01- Reduce Voice Communication

Description: This functional test demonstrates that the devices have enough communication capabilities between them to share data and can transmit information to SIGRUN and the solution provided by Valkyries is compatible with existing communication in emergency scenarios.

Also, we will demonstrate that VALKYRIES achieves a functional framework resulting from the integration of all these elements in a unified SIGRUN interoperable platform able to properly operate on real first-aid response exercises; being deployed at the project demonstration scenarios and demonstrating that data digitalized for triage is available during all the exercise into the SIGRUN platform.

This test is based on a digital triage process to verify the requirements described above, deployed on several terminals, and during the demonstration we verified that the information related to Victims is shared between those different terminals connected to SIGRUN, and that

this information is also integrated into SIGRUN through the integration interface. The data is constantly visualised through the GLOBAL COP. For each UC, a specific URL/API has been deployed and verified in the demonstration.

This test has been carried out for UC#1, UC#2 and UC#3. In all cases it has been verified that sufficient connectivity is available in the standard 4G communications environment to share operational data to enable the management of a multi-casualty incident between countries.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demonstration

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T4.2.1, REQ_COM_T4.2.2, REQ_BASE_T7.3_1, REQ_COM-T4.2.7

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-5; VALK -OBJ-6

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-D01- Reduce Voice Communication
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP4.42
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	<p>During the incident the information shared between the terminals and GLOBAL COP for operational purposes is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Age Group (Adult, Child, Elder) -Gender (Male/Female) -Assistance Status (Waiting for assistance, waiting for evacuation, Evacuated, In destination) -Triage status (AT, ET) -Triage classification -Main Pathology -Transport -Staff reporting information
Pre-processing/Analysis	The information related to victims' status and incident location is created and shared through VALKYRIES to the Command Control Applications.
Premises and limitations	<p>Connectivity between applications is necessary. For this test, 4G has been used. Connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform has been verified before testing.</p> <p>The terminals have been previously configured with the associated users.</p> <p>The vehicles and hospital have been assigned and have not been integrated with the command-and-control tool.</p> <p>Static data of Agencies, staff, assets have been previously created in SIGRUN and have been to be consistent and correct.</p>

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-D01- Reduce Voice Communication
	It has not been tested with all available technologies, it has not been tested with TETRA communications, only conventional 4G communications have been used with the coverage available in the area.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be used in these tests Only the permissions and users necessary for the test will be enabled.
Brief Description of the Test	To carry out the tests during the Use Cases several mobile terminals will be provided in the same location where the UC will be executed. These terminals will be connected to SIGRUN to send data using the available 4G network in each UC. In a first step the incident is created in SIIGRUN by the command-and-control tool and is checked that is accessible to all devices. In a second step the triage process is initialized, and the information is shared between the terminals and visualized in SIGRUN through GLOBAL COP.

Table 8 - Associated tests CO.WP4.42-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-D01	Harmonisation description: The system MUST be able to generate and updated information related to the incident creation and victims
	EM: - Victims Information is created in one device and available between terminals. - Victims Information is integrated into SIGRUN and visualized in GLOBAL COP - Information is shared using 4G available network
	MR: - Triage application updates data in SIGRUN - GLOBAL COP visualizes data from SIGRUN
	KPI: - KPI 1: Information related to incident is available on devices: YES/NO (Available = success) - KPI 2: Information related to victims is available on devices (Available = success) - KPI 3: Information related to victims is available on SIGRUN and is visualized in GLOBAL COP (Available = success) - KPI 4 : Devices are connected to available 4G Network (Connected = success)
	Verification: Test A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (information available YES and time elapsed 100% success) B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed (Information available YES and time elapsed: 50%).

	<p>C: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded</p> <p>(Information available NO and time elapsed: <25%).</p>
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Table 9 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.42-D01

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.1.2.2. CO-WP4-42-D02- Reduce Voice Communication

Description: The information exchanged **MUST** be confidential between the devices involved in the communication.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T4.2_5

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-D02- Reduce Voice Communication
T3 – Functional tests	T3 – Functional tests
Type	T3 – Functional test
Qualification method	Demo
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	N/A
Preprocessing/Analysis	First responders' device/wearables must can communicate with SIGRUN by using HTTPs requests
Premises and limitations	Wearable must have connectivity and SIGRUN must be available. It will be tested before the demonstration.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be used in this demo.
Brief Description of the Test	A wearable will make a HTTPs request to SIGRUN, this way, by using the Wireshark tool, we can read the trace HTTP sent by the wearable. If the body of the HTTPs request is encrypted means that the information sent is protected.

Table 10 - Associated tests CO.WP4.42-D02

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-D02	Harmonisation description:
	<p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data is encrypted and not visible by an attacker.
	<p>MR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Latency: less than 1000ms for every request.

	KPI:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adequacy: 100% messages are encrypted. - Penalties in execution time: less than 10ms
	Verification: Demo
	A: Successful verification. Data sent is encrypted. B: Failed verification. Data sent is not encrypted.

Table 11 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.42-D02

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.1.2.3. CO-WP4-42-D03- Reduce Voice Communication

Description: Each participant and device **MUST** be authenticated in the system.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ-COM-T.4.2.8

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-D03- Reduce Voice Communication
Level	Requirements demonstration
Type	T3 – Functional test
Qualification method	Demo
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	N/A
Preprocessing/Analysis	SIGRUN uses token for authorisation, therefore, the HTTPs requests sent must have a valid token on the header.
Premises and limitations	SIGRUN must be available. It will be tested before the demonstration.
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A
Brief Description of the Test	To validate that SIGRUN implements that authorization token, we will make a HTTPs request to it, and check if the token is included on the header by using Wireshark. Moreover, we must check the response given by SIGRUN when the token is not included or is not valid.

Table 12 - Associated tests CO.WP4.42-D03

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-D03	Harmonisation description:
	EM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requests are authenticated
	MR: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Execution time: Should not affect - Resource consumption: Should not affect
	KPI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adequacy: 100% requests are authenticated by a valid token.
	Verification: Demo A: Successful verification. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Valid token is included and SIGRUN provides a valid response. - Token is not valid and SIGRUN does not provide a valid response - Token is not included and SIGRUN does not provide a valid response B: Failed verification. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Valid token is included and SIGRUN does not provides a valid response. - Token is not valid and SIGRUN provides a valid response - Token is not included and SIGRUN provides a valid response

Table 13 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.42-D03

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.1.2.4. CO-WP4-42-D04- Reduce Voice Communication

Description: Roles **MUST** be assigned to each of the network actors with certain permissions.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T4.2_9

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-D04- Reduce Voice Communication
Level	Requirements demonstration
Type	T3 – Functional test
Qualification method	Demo

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-D04- Reduce Voice Communication
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	N/A
Preprocessing/Analysis	Each application would have to map their internal roles into the SIGRUN roles of the architecture
Premises and limitations	SIGRUN must be available. It will be tested before the demonstration.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be used in this demo.
Brief Description of the Test	An application will try to map their roles into SIGRUN platform. After that, we check which are the established roles.

Table 14 - Associated tests CO.WP4.42-D04

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-D04	Harmonisation description:
	EM:
	- Roles are assigned to organization, giving them certain roles
	MR:
	- Execution time: Should not affect
	- Resource consumption: Should not affect
KPI:	
- Adequacy: 100%.	
Verification: Demo	
A: Successful verification.	
- The application registered has to be roles according to their personal application	
B: Failed verification.	
- Roles are not assigned	

Table 15 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.42-D04

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.1.2.5. CO-WP4-42-D05- Reduce Voice Communication**Description:**

The aim of this demonstration is to validate these requirements.

VALKYRIES **SHALL** design a framework supporting the harmonisation and pre-standardisation of cross-sectorial, cross-border, cross-hierarchical resource federation.

The inter-institutional collaboration requirements will be analysed thoroughly, adapting the resource federation framework with the interoperability harmonized abilities to handle the multi-domain scenario being explored in VALKYRIES.

The different actors using the platform **MUST** have mechanisms to communicate in a secure and trusted way.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T6.1_2, REQ_BASE_T6.1_3, REQ_COM_T6.1_5

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-42-D05- Reduce Voice Communication
Level	Requirements demonstration
Type	T3 – Functional test
Qualification method	Demo
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information sent by devices or wearables of first responders
Preprocessing/Analysis	The SIGRUN platform must be capable of acquiring multidomain data, such as, first responses in different countries, and integrate it the same platform. Moreover, the information interchanged in the communication must be encrypted.
Premises and limitations	Wearables must have connectivity and SIGRUN must be available. It will be tested before the demonstration.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be used in this demo.
Brief Description of the Test	Different first responders from different countries will send their acquired data to SIGRUN and it must be integrated in the same platform. Moreover, if test 2 and 5 are successful, the data in the communication is secured.

Table 16 - Associated tests CO.WP4.42-D05

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-D05	Harmonisation description:
	EM: - SIGRUN handles multidomain data.
	MR: - Latency: less than 1000ms for every request.
	KPI: - Adequacy: 100% messages

	- Penalties in execution time: less than 10ms
	Verification: Demo
	A: Successful verification.
	- SIGRUN is capable of handling multidomain data, such as, data from first responses in different countries, and integrate it in the same platform
	B: Failed verification.
	- SIGRUN is not capable of handling multidomain data, such as, data from first responses in different countries, and integrate it in the same platform

Table 17 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.42-D05

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.2. CO.WP4.28- Cross border data trace

This harmonisation opportunity has been verified only by test.

Description:

This test consists of verifying and validating that the data created digitally from the all federated systems attached to SIGRUN (Wearables track and trace, external sources etc.) is shared through SIGRUN and is accessible to the rest of the Command-and-Control applications in cross border incidents (iSafety and Global COP) that have the necessary permissions to view this information.

Considerations:

Bi-lateral agreements on data exchange between countries need to be considered. Not all data are allowed to be shared for cross border trace.

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T4.3_22

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7

Associated test

Test ID	CO-WP4-28-T01- Cross border data trace.
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP4.28
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	Limitations on data sharing due to bilateral countries agreements
Information to collect	Interfaces through APIs from all attached federated systems in SIGRUN and external resources must be mapped in Common Operational Picture synchronized between different involved

	countries in the incident. All data and metadata exchanged between such systems are logged in secure blockchain network
Preprocessing/Analysis	Execution of the functionality on the demonstrator and inspection of the result. The same tactical information and victims' status/position must be mapped in both COPs
Premises and limitations	Federated systems must comply to SIGRUN standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Log into SIGRUN following the specified procedures defined (Risk assessment and Internal Procedures, ID5.4) APIs providing the interconnection must follow the SIGRUN architecture defined in D2.8 Data exchanges will be on the minimum data set structure defined in D2.8 Data and metadata of related transactions will be logged in blockchain networks
Security and Privacy Considerations	It is assumed that the infrastructure involved complies with the relevant security and privacy policies defined in D7.4 [6]. The resulting reports and information will be treated according to the contractually predefined levels of access and dissemination restrictions.
Brief Description of the Test	On the deployed demonstrator, test the possibility of configuration and networks. Check the result on the virtualized scenario against actual and/or simulated data The result will be a calculation of the percentage of possible flexibility in configuration. In a complementary way, the number of resources consumed during the execution of the test battery will be tested, as well as its execution/response time on COPs

Table 18 - Associated tests CO.WP4.28-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-28-T01	Harmonisation description: the system MUST be able to generate the same tactical information mapping in different COPs operating in the command centres: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Within one country Between countries Based on the limitations for cross-border data exchange
	EM: Measures of mission success from the point of view of stakeholders.
	MR: Used to determine whether the system meets the performance harmonization opportunities needed to meet the EMs. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Execution time (ms); less than 5ms IT resource consumption (memory, CPU) Independent of the number of victims and the agents' resources involved in a cross-border incident

	KPI: Data Security and Transparency through data encryption and logging in secure blockchain network
	Verification: Test, with the following valuation spectrum: A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (the best possible performance was observed). B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed. High adequacy (90%). Small cost in execution time or resources. C: Successful verification. The results are in line with expectations. Average approval. High adequacy (70%). Resource cost less than 50%. D: Successful verification. There is a wide range of improvements to be considered in future work. Conditionally approved. Minimum degree of approval. Sufficient adequacy (>50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources. Automation of data exchanges allowed based on more flexible dynamic criteria supported by AI technologies E: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded

Table 19 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.28-T01

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.3. CO.WP4.2- Logistics assistance using UAVs

This harmonisation opportunity has been verified only by test.

Description: This test consists of verifying, validating and evaluating the use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), also known as drones, for assisting logistics in a first response mission. This assistance can be in the form of transporting low weight equipment and/or consumables between first responders' teams or between a command post and a first responder team. Any UAV can be used, as long as it is possible to attach a small package to it. Both multirotors and fixed-wing drones can be used. It is recommended that if fixed-wing drones are used, they should have vertical-take-off-and-landing (VTOL) capabilities.

Considerations: This test should be conducted with respect to user needs and expectations.

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T4.1_2

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6,

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-2-T01-Logistics assistance using UAVs
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO-WP4-2
Type	Functional test
Qualification method	Test/Demo
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	<p>Test results: All the steps taken before, during and after the mission.</p> <p>Description of the system: Which brand and model; drone firmware version; remote control firmware version; tablet or mobile phone brand, model, operating system version (if a device is attached to the remote control of the drone); package size (WxHxL); package weight; distance.</p> <p>User information: Needs; expectations and feedback.</p> <p>Identified problems: Problems identified during testing.</p>
Pre-processing/Analysis	Usability testing: Write a report in the mission briefing about the expectations and go through the campaign checklist.
Premises and limitations	<p>Simulation premise: The test will be done in good weather to reduce risks. However, in real conditions, the weather may not be good.</p> <p>Resource constraints: Testing may be limited by the distance between first responders' teams.</p> <p>Access limitations: The air traffic may be restricted in the area.</p>
Security and Privacy Considerations	<p>No personal data will be used in these tests.</p> <p>The person conducting the test must have the licenses and permissions to fly the drone in the test area.</p>
Brief Description of the Test	Two first responders' teams (with at least one person in each team) should be placed in a distance shorter than the maximum range of the UAV remote controller. The first team will attach a small package with equipment or consumables to the UAV. This can be for example an extra radio transmitter, a smartphone, batteries, first aid kit, among others. The drone pilot of the first team will take-off the drone, fly to the second team and land the drone. The second team will then detach the package and inform the pilot that the drone is ready to be returned. The pilot will then take-off the drone, fly back to their location and land the drone.

Table 20 - Associated tests CO.WP4-2-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-42-T01	Harmonisation description: An UAV must be used to transport a package between two individuals working in the first response mission.
	EM: Measures of mission success from the point of view of stakeholders. - Access to the package by the second team. - Time of mission per distance between teams discounting the attachment and detachment of the package. - Number of incidents in the mission, for example, almost crashing, hitting something with the drone, loss of signal, unable to return, etc. - Satisfaction of stakeholders (subjective analysis in a range from 0 to 100% of satisfaction).
	MR: Used to determine whether the system meets the performance harmonization opportunities needed to meet the EMs. - Logistics assistance (transport package between first responder teams) with the use of flying drones succeeds.
	KPI: - KPI 1: Package received: YES/NO - KPI 2: Time of mission per distance between teams: < x min/km - KPI 3: Number of reported incidents in mission - KPI 4: Stakeholder satisfaction: A subjective favourable perception by stakeholders
	Verification: Test A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (Package received YES, zero incidents, time of mission per distance between teams smaller than 5 min/km and stakeholder satisfaction over 80%) B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (Package received YES, maximum one incident, time of mission per distance between teams smaller than 10 min/m and stakeholder satisfaction over 50%). C: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded (Package received NO or time of mission per distance

	<i>between teams greater than 10 min/m or stakeholder satisfaction under 50%).</i>
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Table 21 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4-2-T01

Results and evidence will be provided in demonstration stage of VALKYRIES use cases

4.4. CO.WP4.15 – Location of near/nearest vehicles

This harmonisation opportunity has been verified only by test.

Description: The procedure here in described aims to validate the opportunity CO.WP4.15: Location of near/Nearest vehicles, and the requirements / solution that contribute to support the Opportunity.

Considerations: N/A.

Verification Method: Demonstration

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T4.1_2, REQ_COM_T4.3_7, REQ_COM_T4.5_2, REQ_COM_T4.5_9, REQ_COM_T4.5_10, REQ_COM_T4.5_11, REQ_COM_T4.5_15

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-15-T01-Location of Nearest Vehicles
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP4.15
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Verification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Regular gathering and dissemination to the applicable command centres (Operational command centre and medical command centre) of the MCI events vehicles. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vehicle ID - Vehicle location (Lat / Long) - Vehicle characterization (plate number, organization owner, type) - Vehicle status: availability and ops status (On duty; On scene; Off duty)
Preprocessing/Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The vehicle location data (defined above) is shared via the VALKYRIES mechanism (SIGRUN) with the command centres; - Vehicles position is displayed in the map together with the victims' position, allowing situation managers to assign the nearest available vehicles to the victims. - Vehicle assigned to transport a victim from incident to a hospital / medical centre regularly reports its location, from the moment of departure to the moment of arrival at the destination.
Premises and limitations	The following premises are assumed to perform the validation:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-15-T01-Location of Nearest Vehicles
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IP mobile communication coverage is available, properly connecting and functioning and providing needed bandwidth; - The communications infrastructure provides the required security (bellow network level) - To account for GPDR restrictions the actors' data registered in the tests will be based on an alias. <p>The following limitations and mitigations were considered to perform the validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When no real vehicles are available (Due to logistics) or are not equipped to report location (GPS and communications), the transportation of the victim from the incident location to the destination location will be simulated.
Security and Privacy Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The communication above IP will use HTTPS or encryption other means of encryption. - Private data is not accessed or used within the tests. - All the tools and users are accounts will be previously created specifically for the purposes of the tests.
Brief Description of the Test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The simulacrum tests will be executed. Static Scenario data will be uploaded to the system prior to the test. - Initial vehicles data is displayed in the command centre. - Once a victim is required to be transported to the medical centre / Hospital, the operation coordinator (or similar) will allocate the nearest available ambulance to the victim. - The ambulance initiates the transportation of the victims top the destination. <p>Recorded data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At any step of the procedure, a time stamp will be collected and recorded. - all information exchanged are recorded; - Updated position of the vehicle will be recorded

Table 22 - Associated test CO.WP4-15-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-15-T01	Harmonisation description: The system MUST be able to generate an updated vehicles position picture that support the Operational Command to make better time dependent victims evacuation decisions
	EM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vehicles position elapsed time between the real position and the information updated in the command centre: < 2 minute
	MR: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vehicles position know at the command centre - Vehicles position updates within a gape time bellow 2 minutes - Vehicles destination capable of estimating a vehicle ETA

	<p>KPI: Defined by stakeholders as measures of the minimum and critical performance of the system or process, as well as its level of acceptance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Yes= success)- KPI 2: Updated position of vehicles: < 5 minutes 100 % success; 5 to 8 minutes: 90% success 9 to 10 minutes: 50% success; > 10 minutes 0% success- KPI 3: time elapsed (since the vehicles position to the updated position at the Operational centre)<ul style="list-style-type: none">- < 2 minutes 100 % success- Between 2 and 4 minutes 50 % success- 4 to 5 minutes 25% success> 5 minutes 0 % success
	<p>Verification: Test with the following valuation spectrum:</p> <p>A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed: Data is shared at the command centre displaying correct position of the vehicles and a short updating elapsed time (2 < minutes)</p> <p>B: Successful verification. Information shared and available at the Command centre but presents at least one important information: a high delay (> 2 minutes and < 5 minutes); or incorrect assets position. Minimum degree of approval.</p> <p>C: Failed verification. Information not provided at the command centre or not complying with any of the two above conditions.</p>

Table 23 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.15-T01

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.5. CO.WP4.55- Use of wearable to support triage

This harmonisation opportunity has been verified only by test.

Description:

Wearables (bracelets), will be used as:

- A system for Identification (assigning a specific ID to each victim) and labelling (making the assigned priority level visible to all first responders) of the casualties of an ICM or disaster
- As a track and trace system for registering victims from ground zero, before their handling to a qualified EMS first responder
- As a system to track and trace victims of disasters that do not need hospitalization (people/internal refugees that need to be evacuated and moved to safe places by the Authorities)

Considerations:

The same considerations as applied in the Triage opportunity

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T4.5.2

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test

Test ID	CO-WP4-55-T01-Use of wearable to support triage
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO-WP4-55-T01
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Interfaces, data models, limitations of the technological deployment environment are the same as in the Triage opportunity
Preprocessing/Analysis	Execution of the functionality on the demonstrator and inspection of the result as per the use of wearables in triage Demonstration of track and trace capabilities using bracelets provided by TASSICA for casualties, and by and ARATOS for evacuated victims that do not need hospitalization
Premises and limitations	Terrestrial communication networks (G3/4/5) must be available. In places where no communication networks are available, store and forward messaging will be used
Security and Privacy Considerations	It is assumed that the infrastructure involved complies with the relevant security and privacy policies as defined in ID5.4. The resulting reports and information will be treated according to the contractually predefined levels of access and dissemination restrictions.
Brief Description of the Test	E.g., On the deployed demonstrator, test the possibility of configuration and networks. Check the result on the virtualized scenario. The result will be a calculation of the percentage of possible flexibility in configuration. In a complementary way, the number of resources consumed during the execution of the test battery will be tested, as well as its execution time.

Table 24 - Associated test CO.WP4-55-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-55-T01	Harmonisation description: the system MUST be able to generate trace data of victims or refugees in COPs as well entries in SIGRUN logging system (blockchain) with accuracy. EM: Measures of mission success from the point of view of stakeholders.
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	<p>MR: Used to determine whether the system meets the performance harmonization opportunities needed to meet the EMs.</p> <p>Execution time (ms); dependant on the network's availability and bandwidth capabilities</p> <p>Resource consumption (memory, CPU). 8GB RAM, 2VMs are required to support the system</p> <p>APPs on first responders' NFC smartphones or tablets require 40MB free storage space</p>
	<p>KPI: Defined by stakeholders as measures of the minimum and critical performance of the system or process, as well as its level of acceptance.</p> <p>Adequacy (%). More than 99%</p> <p>Penalties in execution time (ms) and resource consumption (%). N/A</p>
	<p>Verification: Test with the following valuation spectrum:</p> <p>A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (the best possible performance observed in UC2, 3 and 4 testing). No cost in execution time or resources.</p> <p>B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed. High adequacy (99%). Small cost in execution time or resources.</p> <p>C: Successful verification. The results are in line with expectations. Average approval. High adequacy (70%). Resource cost less than 50%.</p> <p>D: Successful verification. There is a wide range of improvements to be considered in future work as the same tagging system provided by the wearables can be used as the unique ID in other triage systems. Also, the use of NFC wearables as tags on resources (equipment, vehicles, etc.) can be used for non-real time track and trace. Conditionally approved. E.g., Sufficient adequacy (>50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.</p> <p>E: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded</p>

Table 25 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.55-T01

Results sheets and evidence sheets will be provided in the UC Report.

4.6. CO.W4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platform.

4.6.1.1. CO-WP4-21-A01 Historical data analysis from the missions and platform

This harmonisation opportunity has been verified only by Analysis

Description: Analysis of the data acquired to validate if it is representatively enough to be included in the process of dataset building.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Analysis

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T7.2_1, REQ_BASE_T7.2_2, REQ_BASE_T7.2_3, REQ_BASE_T7.2_4, REQ_BASE_T7.2_5, REQ_BASE_T7.2_6, REQ_COM_T7.2_7

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-21-A01 - Historical data analysis from the missions and platform
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP4.21
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demo
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	<p>At the moment, the following information has been analysed, based on the data available in the SIGRUN platform, also related to test ID “Reduce Voice Communication, digitalizing most information exchanges”:</p> <p>Information related to victims:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age Group (Adult, Child, Elder) - Gender (Male/Female) - Assistance Status (Waiting for assistance, waiting for evacuation, Evacuated, In destination) - Triage status (AT, ET) - Triage colour - Main Pathology - Transport - Staff reporting information <p>Information related to the incident:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type of incident - Geolocation - Time of the incident
Pre-processing/Analysis	This test consists in studying the statistical variability of the data previously acquired to ensure that it contains enough variability to build a dataset. The data security is ensured having logged all relevant data and metadata exchanged between different federated systems attached in SIGRUN through their encryption and storage/logging in secure blockchain network
Premises and limitations	Data stored in the SIGRUN platform coming from different sources.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The data analysis process followed must ensure that the data does not contain information that can identify patients. At least, data must be previously anonymized.
Brief Description of the Test	This test consists in studying each of the dimensions and data sources stored in the SIGRUN platform to verify that each one presents enough variability in their values to be later included

Test ID:	CO-WP4-21-A01 - Historical data analysis from the missions and platform
	in the dataset building process. Those sources that do not present variability will be excluded from the dataset.

Table 26 – Associated tests CO.WP4.21-A01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP4-21-A01	Harmonisation description: The system MUST be able to generate the analysis of data stored in the SIGRUN platform to determine if these data are suitable or not for their inclusion in the dataset.
	EM: The data acquired presents sufficient representativeness.
	MR: The 80% of the data acquired presents sufficient representativeness, considering the variability of their values.
	KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Available = success) KPI 2: The 80% of the data acquired presents sufficient representativeness.
	Verification: Analysis, with the following valuation spectrum: A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed in terms of data variability, where preliminary data provided to the SIGRUN platform achieves the requirement of requirement of 80%. However, further analysis during the UC1 must be performed.

Table 27 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.21-A01

Result sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Reports.

4.6.1.2. CO-WP4-21-DO2 Historical data analysis from the missions and platform

Description:

The aim of this demonstration is to validate these requirements.

It is **REQUIRED** to create models allowing the optimisation of decision based on the data obtained from multiple sources.

The models **MUST** be capable of identifying the best decisions to treat subjects belonging to the multiple-victim emergency.

Models **MUST** be obtained for the detection of patients' status by analysing the various bio signals of the patients.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T7.2.1, REQ_COM_T7.2.2, REQ_COM_T7.2.3

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP4-21-D02-Historical Data Analysis from the missions and platform
Level	Requirements demonstration
Type	T3 – Functional test
Qualification method	Demo
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Data from different sources
Preprocessing/Analysis	SIGRUN must be capable of integrating data from multiples sources, such as, specific data for each first responder during an emergency, allowing to analyse the data to create a trained model.
Premises and limitations	SIGRUN must have enough information to create a model more accurate.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be used in this demo.
Brief Description of the Test	With the gathered data during use cases by different sources of different first responders (if test 10 is successful), a trained model will be created in order to identify best decisions during an emergency response.

Table 28 - Associated requirement test CO.WP4.21-D02

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-W CO-WP4-21-D02	Harmonisation description:
	EM:
	- Creation of a model which can speed up tasks in an emergency response.
	MR:
	- Execution time: Time prediction – less than 1000ms
	- System resource consumption: Imperceptible
	KPI:
	- Adequacy: 90%
- Penalties in execution time: 5000ms	
Verification: Demo	
A: Successful verification. (Excellent result) Model has an accuracy higher than 90%	
B: Successful verification. (Very good result) Model has an accuracy higher than 80%	
C: Successful verification. (Average result) Model has an accuracy higher than 70%	

	B: Failed verification. Model has an accuracy lower than 70%
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Table 29 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP4.21-D02

Result sheets and evidence will be reported in the UC report.

5. WP5 - Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses harmonization opportunities

All the harmonisation opportunities identified in VALKYRIES WP5 have been verified by preliminary tests previously performed prior to the Use Cases (UCs) of the Project. Most of them have also been verified by demonstration in UCs 1 to 3.

5.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

Description: The standardization of terminology used by professionals in the field of emergency and disaster planning, preparedness, and response at the EU level is crucial for promoting clarity and consistency in communication, improving efficiency and interoperability.

The VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and implementation (VALKYRIES GLOSSARY) is a web-based multilingual terminology database of technical terms and symbols focused on emergencies and disasters, with the primary objective of improving planning, preparation, communication and coordination among first responders.

The version (prototype) of the VALKYRIES GLOSSARY implemented within the VALKYRIES project lifecycle is not the full proposed enabler itself, but an example of a more limited scope, aligned with the enabler guidelines set out in the deliverable D5.4, to test and validate the usefulness of the proceeding proposal in tests.

It aims to promote a common understanding of terminology and concepts by creating a comprehensive, multilingual, web-based terminology database to serve as a common reference for VALKYRIES researchers in the planning, preparation and execution of the Project's demonstrators.

Its validation was carried out by means of preliminary tests and in the UCs by means of specific surveys.

5.1.1. CO.WP5-1 Verification by Test

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_1, REQ_COM_T5.4_2, REQ_COM_T5.4_3

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: PRELIMINARY TEST
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-1
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test

Test ID:	CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: PRELIMINARY TEST
Special Requirements	No
Information to collect	Information should be collected on how respondents evaluate the usability of the collaborative glossary.
Pre-processing/Analysis	After the design and development phase of the prototype of the enabler CO-WP5-1-T01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution, a Cognitive Walkthrough evaluation is performed as a unit test. (Wharton C, Rieman J, Lewis C, Polson P. <i>The Cognitive Walkthrough: A practitioner's guide</i> . 1994. https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:53925427)
Premises and limitations	The test was conducted with technology experts from the VALKYRIES Consortium. The test provides indications on how to improve the first uses and learning of the interactive digital product. It focuses on the user, on the tasks to be performed and on the aspects that are known to be problematic. Experienced testers are used (the result may be limited or biased by the skills and experience of the tester).
Security and Privacy Considerations	Both those responsible for collecting the questionnaires and those responsible for their analysis will comply with the GDPR. In any case, the results will be published respecting the anonymity of the authors.
Brief Description of the Test	The list of tasks to be carried out during the Cognitive Walkthrough test would be as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Register a new term with a username and password. • Editing an existing term • Consult information of a term • Create a new equivalence of an existing term and then delete it. • Create a new source of documentation for an existing term and then delete it • Delete a term

Table 30 – Associated tests CO.WP5-1-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-1-T01	Harmonisation description: A Cognitive Walkthrough testing of the VALKYRIES Collaborative Glossary is performed as a structured approach to evaluating usability of the prototype prior to its use in the planning of the demonstrators (UCs), using the results obtained to further improve the proposal.
	EM: The problem hypotheses are compiled in three aspects: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Importance (if it seriously affects usability). 2. Frequency (if it occurs many times or few times). 3. Persistence (if it is present for a large part of the journey).

	MR: The estimation of the three aspects (importance, frequency, persistence) of each of the possible problems is evaluated with two possible levels: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Low• High
	KPI: The minimum and critical performance measures established are: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Importance: identify at least 5 problems/areas for improvement (P/AI) rated as low or high importance.• KPI 2: Frequency: more than 65% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency.• KPI 3: Persistence: more than 65% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence.
	Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs: A, Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs). <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Importance: detected 9 problems/areas of improvement (P/AI) (5 rated as HIGH importance and 4 as LOW importance).• KPI 2: Frequency: 77,8% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency.• KPI 3: Persistence: 100% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence. Rating spectrum: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs)• B: Very high adequacy (70-89%)• C: High adequacy (60-79%)• D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%)• E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 31 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-1-T01

Results sheet:

Results sheets will be provided in the UC Report

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in the UC Report.

5.1.2. CO.WP5-1 Verification by Demo

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_2

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-1
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	No
Information to collect	Information should be collected on how respondents assess the acceptance of the proposed unified glossary.
Pre-processing/Analysis	An opinion survey will be conducted on the importance of common terminology for the planning and execution of MCI response.
Premises and limitations	The survey will be open to all participants from all institutions who have used in their tasks of preparation and implementation of each exercise the VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution. The respondents answer the survey anonymously.
Security and Privacy Considerations	Both those responsible for collecting the questionnaires and those responsible for their analysis will comply with the GDPR. In any case, the results will be published respecting the anonymity of the authors.
Brief Description of the Test	The survey will be carried out during the UC2 and UC3 working days.

Table 32 - Associated tests CO.WP5-1-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-1-D01	Harmonisation description: A survey is performed to evaluate the acceptance of the VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution.
	EM: The specific wording of the question raised will be as follows: "Do you think it is important that all emergency services use the same terminology for planning and responding against MCI and disasters?"
	MR: The answer to the question is expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT) and 5 being the most favourable result (TOTALLY AGREED).
	KPI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: The minimum and critical performance measure established is a subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by respondents.
	Verification: Rating according to the total % result. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A: Maximum adequacy (>90%) B: Very high adequacy (70-89%) C: High adequacy (60-79%) D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%) E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 33 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-1-D01

Results sheet:

Results sheets will be provided in the UC Report

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in the UC Report.

5.2. CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans

Description: Information shared in emergency response planning should be harmonized in support of the different entities to understand and easy coordination. To this end, key contingency planning data must be uploaded in a structured way, securely shared and easily retrieved to support C2 leaders during an MCI or disaster.

The STRUCTURED REPOSITORY OF EU EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS (EUR-ERP) is a proposal to provide those responsible for leading the response to cross-border disasters with the information they need to coordinate effectively on the emergency response plans established within the European Union civil protection system.

The version of the EUR-ERP implemented within the VALKYRIES project lifecycle is not the full proposed enabler itself, but a prototype of a more limited scope, aligned with the enabler guidelines set out in the deliverable D5.4, to test and validate the usefulness of the proceeding proposal in tests.

Its objective is to provide those responsible for leading the emergency response in the VALKYRIES use cases (UCs) with the information they need to effectively coordinate the emergency response plans established in the civil protection system of the respective territories involved in each demonstrator.

Its validation was carried out by means of test.

5.2.1. CO.WP5-2 Verification by Test

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_3, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_22, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_11, REQ_COM_T5.4_14, REQ_COM_T5.4_31

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans: TEST
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-2

Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected on how respondents evaluate the usability of the structured repository of emergency plans.
Pre-processing/Analysis	After the design and development phase of the prototype of the enabler CO-WP5-2-T01 - EU structured repository of emergency response plans, a Cognitive Walkthrough evaluation is performed as a unit test. (Wharton C, Rieman J, Lewis C, Polson P. The Cognitive Walkthrough: A practitioner’s guide. 1994. https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:53925427)
Premises and limitations	The test was conducted with expert First Responders from the VALKYRIES Consortium. The test provides indications on how to improve the first uses and learning of the interactive digital product. It focuses on the user, on the tasks to be performed and on the aspects that are known to be problematic. Experienced testers are used (the result may be limited or biased by the skills and experience of the tester).
Security and Privacy Considerations	Both those responsible for collecting the questionnaires and those responsible for their analysis will comply with the GDPR. In any case, the results will be published respecting the anonymity of the authors.
Brief Description of the Test	The list of tasks to be carried out during the Cognitive Walkthrough test would be as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a new Emergency Response Plan (ERP) • Assign agencies involved in an existing ERP • Consult the items of an existing ERP of your own • Edit an existing ERP item • Duplicate an ERP item

Table 34 – Associated tests CO.WP5-2-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-2-T01	Harmonisation description: A Cognitive Walkthrough testing is performed as a structured approach to evaluating the usability of the Structured Repository of EU Emergency Response Plans (EUR-ERP) prototype to provide the key information regarding the emergency response plans involved in the UCs.
	EM: The problem hypotheses are compiled in three aspects: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Importance (if it seriously affects usability). 2. Frequency (if it occurs many times or few times). 3. Persistence (if it is present for a large part of the journey).
	MR: The estimation of the three aspects (importance, frequency, persistence) of each of the possible problems is evaluated with two possible levels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low • High

	<p>KPI: The minimum and critical performance measures established are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Importance: identify at least 5 problems/areas for improvement (P/AI) rated as low or high importance. • KPI 2: Frequency: more than 65% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency. • KPI 3 Persistence: more than 65% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence.
	<p>Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs: A, Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Importance: detected 6 problems/areas of improvement (P/AI) (all of them rated as LOW importance). • KPI 2: Frequency: 66,7% of the detected P/AI rated as LOW frequency. • KPI 3: Persistence: 66,7% of detected P/AI rated as LOW persistence. <p>Rating spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs) • B: Very high adequacy (70-89%) • C: High adequacy (60-79%) • D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%) • E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 35 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-2-T01

Results sheet:

Result sheets will be provided in the UC Report.

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in the UC Report.

5.2.2. CO.WP5-2 Verification by Demo

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_3, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_22, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_11, REQ_COM_T5.4_14, REQ_COM_T5.4_31

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-2-D01 - EU Structured repository of emergency response plans: DEMONSTRATION
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-2
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the access to data relating to emergency response plans specific to the type and location of the incident through a link in the global COP, which leads to the EUR-ERP prototype.
Pre-processing/Analysis	A prior process of identification and uploading to the EUR-ERP prototype of those Emergency Response Plans potentially activated during the response to the UC incident will be carried out.
Premises and limitations	The information functionality of the EUR-ERP is limited, given its prototype character. The evaluation within SIGRUN requires 4G connectivity between the applications. The connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform is checked before the test.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The permissions and users required for the test within SIGRUN, and the Emergency Response Plans information will be enabled taking into account GRPD issues.
Brief Description of the Test	During UC1, the EU ERP prototype developed at VALKYRIES will be tested in real time by the Project researchers involved in the planning and execution of the simulation. The demonstration will be complemented in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform

Table 36 - Associated tests CO.WP5-2-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-2-D01	Evaluating the usability of the Structured Repository of EU Emergency Response Plans (EUR-ERP) prototype to provide the key information regarding the emergency response plans involved in the UC.
	EM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EUR-ERP Availability • EUR-ERP Adequacy • EUR-ERP Operability
	MR: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The compliance will be determined (YES/NO; compliance = success).
	KPI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: EUR-ERP availability: The emergency plans accessed are those specific to the territory and the type of risk concerned. • KPI 2: EUR-ERP adequacy: Adequacy: The emergency plans accessed are those specific to the territory and the type of risk concerned.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 3: EUR-ERP operability: By accessing the EU-ERP via the link in the global COP, the contents of the Emergency Response Plan related to the incident can be consulted in real time.
	<p>Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs.</p> <p>Rating spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs)• B: Very high adequacy (70-89%)• C: High adequacy (60-79%)• D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%)• E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 37 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-2-D01

Results sheet:

Result sheet will be provided in UC Report.

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report.

5.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

The operational procedures of emergency services are very diverse and there is no homogeneity in aspects such as the triage system used, the coding and labelling of victims or the recording of victims' clinical information.

Improving these aspects would facilitate interoperability between services in cross-border and/or multisectoral incidents with multiple victims.

Faced with this reality, to ensure the operability of emergency plans, especially when they are activated to respond to cross-sector and/or cross-border disasters, it is essential to develop tools, not necessarily complex, that enable interoperability between services and regions, facilitating the exchange of information for decision-making and coordination. In relation to this, VALKYRIES Project proposes two enablers to achieve harmonisation and pre-standardisation in the field of MCI triage procedures and labelling.

- Unification of triage regarding priorities and casualty labelling codes in MCI and disasters.
- Standardised triage card TASSICA 3 as a non-technological tool to support traceability, unified prioritisation, interoperability and labelling of victims.

5.4. CO.WP5-7-1 Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level

Description: To facilitate the joint work of first responders from different agencies or areas in responding to the emergency or disaster on the ground, it is necessary to harmonise not only terminology but also certain key criteria to ensure a common understanding of the situation. Unifying the categorisation and labelling code of the priority of victims in an MCI or disaster is one of them.

The VALKYRIES project proposes to establish an EU-wide standardised code to unify the coding and labelling of triage priorities in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters, based primarily on NATO standards. It is proposed to implement a pentapolar triage coding with the following triage priorities and colours for tagging:

- PT 1 IMMEDIATE (Red)
- PT2 DELAYED (Yellow)
- PT3 MINIMAL (Green)
- PT4 EXPECTANT (Blue)
- D DECEASED (Black)

This classification and coding are applied throughout the design and development phases of SIGRUN, in the planning and execution of the VALKYRIES use cases and in the integration of the tools used to support the Project's demonstrators.

Its validation was carried out by means of preliminary tests and in the UCs by means of specific surveys and demonstration within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform in a harmonized way.

5.4.1. CO.WP5-7-1 Verification by Test

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO.WP5-7-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-7
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the use of a common methodology for coding and classifying victims in a MCI.
Pre-processing/Analysis	A questionnaire has been answered by two target groups: one consisting of first responders in training and the other one consisting of first responders integrated in an EMS with professional experience.
Premises and limitations	Execution is based on target groups with prior knowledge of health care in MCI and disasters. The objective of the survey is explained to them, and they answer the survey anonymously.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.

Test ID:	CO.WP5-7-T01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: PRELIMINARY TEST
Brief Description of the Test	<p>Two groups were selected for testing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students of the Emergency Medical Technician course from the ISEP CEU Institute (Castellón, Spain). • Experienced first responders (Doctors, Nurses and Emergency Medical Technicians) from the SUMMA112 service (Madrid, Spain). <p>A briefing session was organised for each of these groups to present the proposed standardisation of priorities and coding of victims of an MCI or disaster.</p> <p>This was followed in both groups by a questionnaire that includes aspects considered key to the analysis of the need for a unified coding and labelling system for victims in MCI and disasters. The questionnaire contains four questions that refer to the following aspects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Importance of EMS using the same classification to designate triage priority in MCI and disasters. 2. Use of a specific name for triage priorities 3. Specific assignment of colours for different triage priorities 4. Assessment of the use of the same classification and colour coding in the EU to facilitate EMS working together in cross-border MCI.

Table 38 – Associated tests CO.WP5-7-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO.WP5-7-T01	Harmonisation description: A pentapolar classification and coding of triage priorities for mass casualty incidents (MCIs) and disasters is proposed for the European Union to facilitate better understanding and interoperability between agencies and territories.
	<p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Degree of importance attached to the use of a common classification and coding of victim priorities in a MCI. • Stakeholder coding agreement: The level of agreement among first responders on the proposed MCI triage categories. • Stakeholder tagging agreement: The level of agreement among first responders on the proposed MCI colour tagging code for victims in MCI and disasters. • Cross-border cooperation improvement: The perceived improvement in cross-border cooperation between EMS when using a standardised classification and coding system.
	<p>MR: The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).</p>

	KPI: The minimum and critical results established are: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 2: Stakeholder coding agreement: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 3: Stakeholder tagging agreement: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 4: Cross-border cooperation improvement: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.
	Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs: A, Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs): FIRST RESPONDERS WITH EXPERTISE: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Relevance: 95,24%• KPI 2: Stakeholder coding agreement: 100,00%• KPI 3: Stakeholder tagging agreement: 100,00%• KPI 4: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100,00% FIRST RESPONDERS IN TRAINING: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Relevance: 100,00%• KPI 2: Stakeholder coding agreement: 100,00%• KPI 3: Stakeholder tagging agreement: 100,00%• KPI 4: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100,00% Rating spectrum: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs)• B: Very high adequacy (70-89%)• C: High adequacy (60-79%)• D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%)• E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 39 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-7-T01

Results sheet:

Results sheet will be provided in the UC Report

Evidence of implementation and compliance

Evidence will be provided in the UC Report

5.4.2. CO.WP5-7-1 Verification by Demo

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated demo:

Test ID:	CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-7
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the C2 managers and First Responders' opinion on the use of a common methodology for coding and classifying victims in the UCs. The degree of compliance in the UCs execution with the recommendations regarding the standardised classification and coding (colour) of victims proposed by the VALKYRIES Project will also be checked in UC1, UC2 and UC3.
Pre-processing/Analysis	A questionnaire has been developed to collect respondents' opinions on the standardized coding and classifying victims proposed by VALKYRIES Project in the UCs. The information related to victims' triage coding will be created and shared through SIGRUN to the C2 applications.
Premises and limitations	The survey will be conducted on the days of the UCs 2 and 3. It will be open to all responders from the emergency services involved in the exercise. The respondents will answer the survey anonymously. Connectivity 4G between applications is required for the evaluation within SIGRUN. The connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform will be verified prior to the test. The terminals will be previously configured with the associated users.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The questionnaires will be anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs will be known. The permissions and users required for the test within SIGRUN will be enabled taking into account GRPD issues.
Brief Description of the Test	The survey will be carried out during the UC2 and UC3 working days. It contains 3 questions that refer to the following aspects: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Importance of EMS using the same classification to designate triage priority in MCI and disasters. 2. Specific assignment of colours for different triage priorities 3. Assessment of the use of the same classification and colour coding in the EU to facilitate EMS working together in cross-border MCI. The degree of compliance with the proposed standardised classification and coding (colour) of victims during the UCs will be assessed on the basis of the data recorded in SIGRUN during the conduct of each UC.

Table 40 - Associated tests CO.WP5-7-1-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO.WP5-7-1-D01	Harmonisation description: The proposed pentapolar classification and coding of triage priorities for mass casualty incidents (MCIs) and disasters is accepted and used in UCs.
	<p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Degree of importance attached to the use of a common classification and coding of victim priorities in a MCI. • Stakeholder coding and labelling agreement: The level of agreement among first responders on the proposed MCI triage categories and colors. • Cross-border cooperation improvement: The perceived improvement in cross-border cooperation between EMS when using a standardised classification and coding system. • UC coding standardisation compliance: The degree of adherence in the UC to the standardised classification and coding of MCI victims proposed by VALKYRIES.
	<p>MR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The answers to the questionnaires will be expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED). • The compliance with the standardised classification and coding proposed by VALKYRIES will be determined for each UC (YES/NO; compliance = success).
	<p>KPI: The minimum and critical results established are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and labelling agreement: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 4: Coding compliance: The information related to the triage of victims in SIGRUN complies with the standardised classification and coding proposed by VALKYRIES: YES (= success)
	<p>Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs.</p> <p>Rating spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs) • B: Very high adequacy (70-89%) • C: High adequacy (60-79%) • D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%) • E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 41 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-7-1-D01

Results sheet:

Results sheet will be provided in the UC Report

Evidence of implementation and compliance

Evidence will be provided in the UC Report

5.5. CO.WP5-7-2 TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters

Description: Given the heterogeneity of the composition and functioning of EMSs in different EU territories, the standardisation of their operational procedures becomes a task, if not impossible, then very difficult and probably very long term. In the meantime, it is necessary to look for faster and more effective solutions that allow for greater operational interoperability of the different emergency services working together.

VALKYRIES proposes the use of a same standardised tool (TASSICA 3 standardised triage card) for the recording of key casualty information by the different emergency services that may intervene in a MCI could be a very simple but very effective element to promote interoperability between services (professional or voluntary, civilian or military), equity in terms of prioritisation of treatment, recording of casualty information and traceability in mass casualty incidents and disasters.

In the preliminary tests and in several of the UCs of the Project, TASSICA 3 triage cards have been used throughout the entire process of victim care at the scene of an MCI: from the first triage to determine the priority of care, to the evacuation of the victims and their reception at the destination hospital.

The evaluation of this proposed enabler has been done both from a subjective point of view by collecting and analysing the opinions of the first responders involved in the preliminary tests and demonstrators, and from an objective point of view by means of determinations collected in the demonstrators.

5.5.1. CO.WP5-7-2 Verification by Test

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.1_10, REQ_COM_T5.1_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-7-T02 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-7
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test

Test ID:	CO-WP5-7-T02 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the use of the TASSICA card once it has been used in the trial.
Pre-processing/Analysis	A questionnaire has been answered by two target groups: one consisting of first responders in training and the other one consisting of first responders integrated in an EMS with professional experience.
Premises and limitations	Execution is based on target groups with prior knowledge of health care in MCI and disasters. The objective of the survey is explained to them, and they answer the survey anonymously.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.
Brief Description of the Test	<p>The starting point is two target groups with previous knowledge of health care in MCI and disasters of different levels.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The first group consists of trainees: Students of the Emergency Medical Technician course from the ISEP CEU Institute (Castellón, Spain). After receiving basic training on health care in MCI and the use of the triage card, they carry out an exercise in which they have to use the card to triage fictitious victims. They then complete the questionnaire. • The second group consists of EMS personnel with pre-hospital experience: Doctors, nurses and paramedics participants in MCI exercises for the preliminary testing of the VALKYRIES proposals, organised by SUMMA 112 at the Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE) in Madrid (Spain). These personnel act as first responders in an MCI drill, assuming the different roles in the victims care using the proposed triage card. Just after the exercise, they answer the questionnaire. <p>The questionnaire includes questions on the following aspects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Extent to which the card helps to homogenise triage priorities, decide on lifesaving gestures, ensure traceability of a victim, and facilitates the recording of health information. 2. Measure in which its use reduces the stress of healthcare staff in decision making. 3. Assessment of its use in facilitating joint EMS work in cross-border MCI. 4. Rating on enabling more efficient execution of tasks in a MCI compared to other cards. 5. Overall level of satisfaction

Table 42 – Associated tests CO.WP5-7-T02

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-7-T02	Title Harmonisation description: VALKYRIES Project proposes the TASSICA 3 triage card as a standardised triage card for emergency services that may be involved in a mass casualty incident, in order to ensure interoperability between services (professional or volunteer, civil or military), equity in treatment prioritisation, recording of victim information and traceability in mass casualty incidents and disasters.
	<p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card. • Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the TASSICA triage card, as measured by self-reported score. • Traceability: the extent to which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the scene of an MCI. • Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of ease of recording complete and accurate victim information using the TASSICA triage card. • First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations. • Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by first responders. • Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA triage card, as perceived by first responders. • Overall satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card.
	<p>MR: The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).</p>
	<p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 3: Traceability: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 6: ask execution efficiency: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 8: Overall satisfaction with the TASSICA 3 triage card enabler. A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.
	<p>Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs: A, Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs):</p> <p>FIRST RESPONDERS WITH EXPERTISE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 100,00%• KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 100,00%• KPI 3: Traceability: 90,48%• KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 95,24%• KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 90,48%• KPI6: Task execution efficiency: 100,00%• KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 95,25%• KPI 8: Overall satisfaction: 100,00% <p>FIRST RESPONDERS IN TRAINING:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 100,00%• KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 100,00%• KPI 3: Traceability: 100,00%• KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 100,00%• KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 100,00%• KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 100,00%• KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 100,00%• KPI 8: Overall satisfaction: 100,00% <p>Rating spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs)• B: Very high adequacy (70-89%)• C: High adequacy (60-79%)• D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%)• E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 43 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-7-T02

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report

5.5.2. CO.WP5-7-2 Verification by Demo**Considerations:** N/A**Verification Method:** Demo**Type:** Functional**Traceability with identified requirements:** REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-7
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the use of the enabler, TASSICA 3 triage card, on the UCs 2,3 and 4. The effectiveness of this enabler will also be evaluated in UC1 (hospital perspective), UC2, UC3 and UC4 (prehospital perspective).
Pre-processing/Analysis	A questionnaire will be developed to collect respondents' opinions on the TASSICA 3 triage card. A data sheet will be defined to record the information related to TASSICA 3 triage card during the UC execution.
Premises and limitations	The survey will be open to all the First Responders involved in the exercise. The respondents will answer the survey anonymously. The number and location of observers required during the execution of the UC will be defined in order to carry out the data collection for a proper evaluation of the proposed enabler.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The questionnaires will be anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs will be known. The personal details of the victims used during UC exercise will be fictitious.
Brief Description of the Test	The questionnaire includes questions on the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Extent to which the card helps to homogenise triage priorities, decide on lifesaving gestures, ensure traceability of a victim, and facilitates the recording of health information. 2. Measure in which its use reduces the stress of healthcare staff in decision making. 3. Assessment of its use in facilitating joint EMS work in cross-border MCI. 4. Rating on enabling more efficient execution of tasks in a MCI compared to other procedures. 5. Overall level of satisfaction During the execution of the UC, the VALKYRIES observers will record the data necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed harmonisation solution (TASSICA 3 triage card).

Table 44 - Associated tests CO.WP5-7-2-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-7-2-D01	Title Harmonisation description: TASSICA 3 triage card usefulness as a standardised triage card for emergency services involved in the UCs, in order to ensure interoperability, equity in treatment prioritisation, recording of victim information and traceability.
	EM: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card.• Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the TASSICA triage card, as measured by self-reported score.• Traceability: the extent to which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the scene of an MCI.• Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of ease of recording complete and accurate victim information using the TASSICA triage card.• First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations.• Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by first responders.• Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA triage card, as perceived by first responders.• Stakeholder satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card.• Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.• Triage accuracy: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.
	MR: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).• Time to triage: time from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions (in seconds).• Triage accuracy rate: calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage (%).
KPI: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 3: Traceability: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 8: Stakeholder satisfaction: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 9: Time to triage threshold: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).• KPI 10: Triage accuracy rate: Minimum 80% of correct of correctly triaged casualties made using the TASSICA triage card.
	<p>Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs.</p> <p>Rating spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs)• B: Very high adequacy (70-89%)• C: High adequacy (60-79%)• D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%)• E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 45 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-7-2-D01

Results sheet:

Results sheets will be provided in UC Report

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report

5.6. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

Description: During the management of an MCI or a disaster, information is generated and needs to be shared between the different services involved to ensure proper coordination of the response. However, different emergency services often collect data that are not equally relevant to each other and are not standardised, making interoperability difficult.

To support decision-making by all actors involved (including in cross-border incidents), the establishment of a common federated system for sharing emergency response information requires a standard data taxonomy, syntax and data model. Identifying and standardising what minimum data is necessary for proper incident management is essential for healthcare and decision-making.

In this context, the D2.3/D2.8 deliverable includes SIGRUN's Minimum Data Set (MDS) to identify the entities used in the federation. This data is grouped into different blocks, one of which corresponds to the victims.

The Minimum Data Set to be shared by Emergency Medical Services (EMS MDS) in relation to victims in an MCI or disaster was defined in the D5.4 deliverable by a group of experts using a combination of a Delphi variant with virtual meetings and the Ulstein technique. This EMS MDS includes data related to victim identification, characteristics, victim type, precautions, contact person, location, injuries, health follow-up data and other information related to the person.

The EMS MDS defined in deliverable D5.4 was used as a reference for the development of SIGRUN and for the integration of the different software tools used in the project demonstrators by the emergency services involved in the use cases (UCs).

Its validation was carried out by means of preliminary tests and in the UCs by means of specific surveys and demonstration within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform in a harmonized way.

5.6.1. CO.WP5-12 Verification by Test

Considerations: N/A.

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_3, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_22, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_11, REQ_COM_T5.4_14, REQ_COM_T5.4_31

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-12-T01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-12
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the data exchanged during the trial.
Pre-processing/Analysis	A questionnaire has been developed to collect respondents' opinions on the usefulness of the data exchanged in the management of a MCI.

Test ID:	CO-WP5-12-T01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: PRELIMINARY TEST
Premises and limitations	The questionnaire has been answered by first responders of an EMS who have professional experience after conducting a MCI response trial.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the author is known to the institution to which he/she belongs.
Brief Description of the Test	<p>Doctors, nurses and paramedics participate in a trial of MCI is carried out, organised by SUMMA 112 at the Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE) in Madrid (Spain), with the participation of personnel with experience in emergencies (first responders, disaster managers, technological developers). During the rehearsal, the different elements necessary for the activation and implementation of a care procedure for an incident of this type are deployed, such as: the declaration of the incident, the control of the area, the triage of the victims, their stabilisation and their evacuation and the C2 actions.</p> <p>For this purpose, roles are defined that carry out the different care and C2 tasks, each of which generates data that are displayed and shared.</p> <p>At the end of the simulation, the first responders answer the questionnaire anonymously. This questionnaire contains questions referring to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opinion on whether the data transmitted in the test are appropriate for the proper management of casualties by an EMS in MCI or disasters. Whether the data exchanged has been useful to complete their care tasks.

Table 46 – Associated tests CO.WP5-12-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-12-T01	Harmonisation description: VALKYRIES proposes a minimum data set (EMS MDS) to be shared in MCI and disasters by EMS in relation to victim care.
	<p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data relevance: The perceived relevance of the data exchanged during the trial for proper management of casualties by EMS in an MCI or disaster. Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the exchanged data in the performance of care tasks by first responders.
	MR: The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).
	KPI:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 2: Data usefulness: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.
	<p>Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs: A, Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 100,00% <p>Rating spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs) • B: Very high adequacy (70-89%) • C: High adequacy (60-79%) • D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%) • E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 47 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-12-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report

5.6.2. CO.WP5-12 Verification by Demo

Considerations: N/A.

Verification Method: Demo

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-12
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the data exchanged during the MCI exercise.
Pre-processing/Analysis	A questionnaire will be developed to collect respondents' opinions on the usefulness of the data exchanged in the management of the exercise.

Test ID:	CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION
Premises and limitations	The questionnaire will be open to all participants in all roles deployed during the exercises in the UCs 2 and 3.
Security and Privacy Considerations	<p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the author is known to the institution to which he/she belongs.</p> <p>The permissions and users required for the test within SIGRUN will be enabled taking into account GRPD issues.</p> <p>The personal details of the victims used during the exercise will be fictitious.</p>
Brief Description of the Test	<p>An MCI exercise will be deployed, with defined roles and tasks: search & rescue, C2, EMS, security, etc., each of which generates data that are displayed and shared in real time. SIGRUN is used as the information exchange system. For the demo, various technological and software tools will be used to support responders, all of which are federated in SIGRUN. After the drill, the participants will answer a questionnaire containing questions referring to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opinion on whether the data transmitted in the test are appropriate for the proper management of casualties by an EMS in MCI or disasters. Whether the data exchanged has been useful to complete their care tasks.

Table 48 - Associated tests CO.WP5-12-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-12-D01	Harmonisation description: VALKYRIES EMS minimum data set (EMS MDS) usefulness to data sharing related to victims care in the UCs.
	EM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data relevance: The perceived relevance of the data exchanged during the trial for proper management of casualties by EMS in an MCI or disaster. Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the exchanged data in the performance of care tasks by first responders.
	MR: <p>The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).</p>
	KPI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: Data relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. KPI 2: Data usefulness: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.
	Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs.

	<p>Rating spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs) • B: Very high adequacy (70-89%) • C: High adequacy (60-79%) • D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%) • E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)
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Table 49 -Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-12-D01

Results sheet:

Result sheet will be provided in UC Report

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report

5.7. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

Description: SIGRUN provides a common framework that allows components (e.g., services, applications and systems) to join the VALKYRIES federation of applications and to offer their services and access existing services.

In the VALKYRIES preliminary tests and demonstrations, SIGRUN will be used to federate a set of interconnected technological solutions to support shared situational awareness in response to a multi-casualty incident or disaster. For the development of the tests, these technological solutions have been integrated into the operational procedures of each of the emergency services involved in the use cases (UCs). In this sense, the modifications made to the usual procedures of each service were kept to a minimum to facilitate the comparison of the results obtained and the evaluation of the specific impact attributable to SIGRUN in this context.

Through SIGRUN, information-sharing procedures related to C2, logistics, deployment and provision of medical assistance by EMS first responders could be significantly improved, enabling a more effective response at the scene of a disaster.

Its validation was carried out by means of preliminary tests and in the UCs by means of specific surveys and demonstration within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform in a harmonized way.

5.7.1. CO.WP5-13 Verification by Test

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements:			
REQ_COM_T5.1_7,	REQ_COM_T5.1_8,		
REQ_COM_T5.1_11,	REQ_COM_T5.1_12,	REQ_COM_T5.2_2,	REQ_COM_T5.2_4,
REQ_COM_T5.2_5,	REQ_COM_T5.2_6,	REQ_COM_T5.2_7,	REQ_COM_T5.2_8,
REQ_COM_T5.2_9,	REQ_COM_T5.2_10,	REQ_COM_T5.2_11,	REQ_COM_T5.2_12,
REQ_COM_T5.2_13,	REQ_COM_T5.2_14,	REQ_COM_T5.2_2,	REQ_COM_T5.2_4,
REQ_COM_T5.2_5,	REQ_COM_T5.2_6,	REQ_COM_T5.2_7,	REQ_COM_T5.2_8,
REQ_COM_T5.2_9,	REQ_COM_T5.2_10,	REQ_COM_T5.2_11,	REQ_COM_T5.2_12,

REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_2,
 REQ_COM_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7,
 REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_14,
 REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18,
 REQ_COM_T5.3_19, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22,
 REQ_BASE_T5.4_1, REQ_BASE_T5.4_2, REQ_BASE_T5.4_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_1,
 REQ_COM_T5.4_2, REQ_COM_T5.4_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_4, REQ_COM_T5.4_5,
 REQ_COM_T5.4_6, REQ_COM_T5.4_8, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10,
 REQ_COM_T5.4_11, REQ_COM_T5.4_12, REQ_COM_T5.4_13, REQ_COM_T5.4_14,
 REQ_COM_T5.4_15, REQ_COM_T5.4_16, REQ_COM_T5.4_17, REQ_COM_T5.4_18,
 REQ_COM_T5.4_19, REQ_COM_T5.4_28, REQ_COM_T5.4_29, REQ_COM_T5.4_30,
 REQ_COM_T5.4_31, REQ_COM_T5.4_32, REQ_COM_T5.4_33, REQ_COM_T5.4_34

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-13-T01 - SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-13
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the information sharing procedures associated with the logistics, deployment and on-scene care of an MCI with SIGRUN, once used in the trial.
Pre-processing/Analysis	A questionnaire has been developed to gather the opinion of respondents on the usefulness of SIGRUN in improving information exchange procedures associated with logistics, deployment and health care by first responders in an MCI or disaster.
Premises and limitations	The questionnaire has been answered by first responders integrated in an EMS with professional experience.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the author is known to the institution to which he/she belongs.
Brief Description of the Test	<p>A trial of MCI is carried out, organised by SUMMA 112 at the Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE) in Madrid (Spain), with the participation of personnel with experience in emergencies (first responders, disaster managers, technological developers). During the rehearsal, the different elements necessary for the activation and implementation of a care procedure for an incident of this type are deployed.</p> <p>For this purpose, roles are defined that carry out the different care and C2 tasks, each of which generates data that are displayed and shared.</p>

<p>Test ID:</p>	<p>CO-WP5-13-T01 - SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST</p>
	<p>SIGRUN is used as the information exchange system. For the test, various technological and software tools were used to support first responders (C2, COP, etc.), all of which are federated in SIGRUN.</p> <p>During the course of the intervention, data is generated and must be updated and shared in the system in real time.</p> <p>At the end of the simulation, the first responders answer the questionnaire anonymously. This questionnaire contains questions referring to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between services. • Extent to which the tested procedure would allow a more efficient execution of assigned tasks in a MCI compared to the current situation. • Opinion on whether this system would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to an MCI • Opinion on the ease and simplicity of implementation by a first responder in a MCI • Opinion on the improvement of the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in a MCI • Added value to the management and response in a MCI affecting several communities or countries • Overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged. • Degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.

Table 50 – Associated tests CO.WP5-13-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

<p>CO-WP5-13-T01</p>	<p>Harmonisation description: SIGRUN provides a common framework that allows emergency services to federate a set of interlinked capabilities to work together to support shared situational awareness in response to a multi-casualty incident or disaster.</p> <p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information exchange facilitation: The perceived improvement in information exchange between services using SIGRUN. • Task execution efficiency: The perceived improvement in the efficiency of task execution in an MCI using SIGRUN compared to the current situation. • Integration and cooperation: The perceived improvement in integration and cooperation with other services and/or procedures in responding to an MCI using SIGRUN.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Implementation ease: The perceived ease and simplicity of implementing SIGRUN by first responders in an MCI.• First responder well-being: The perceived improvement in the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in an MCI using SIGRUN.• Added value in cross-border MCI management: The perceived added value of using SIGRUN for managing and responding to an MCI affecting several communities or countries.• Satisfaction with information content: The overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged using SIGRUN.• Satisfaction with the operational procedure: The degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.
	<p>MR: The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).</p>
	<p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 4: Implementation ease: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 5: First responder well-being: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operational procedure: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.

	<p>Verification:</p> <p>Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs: A, Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 100,00%• KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 100,00%• KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 96,00%• KPI 4: Implementation ease: 196,00%• KPI 5: First responder well-being: 100,00%• KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 100,00%• KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 100,00%
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operational procedure: 100,00% <p>Rating spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs) • B: Very high adequacy (70-89%) • C: High adequacy (60-79%) • D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%) • E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)
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Table 51 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-13-T01

Results sheet:

Result sheet will be provided in UC Report.

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report.

5.7.2. CO.WP5-13 Verification by Demo

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_9, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18, REQ_COM_T5.3_19, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-13
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the information sharing procedures associated with the logistics, deployment and on-scene care of an MCI with SIGRUN. To objectively assess the real impact of the SIGRUN proposals on the effectiveness of operational procedures in MCI, the

	analysis of real-time records in SIGRUN during the UC will also be used.
Pre-processing/Analysis	<p>A questionnaire will be developed to gather the opinion of respondents on the usefulness of SIGRUN in improving procedures associated with logistics, deployment and health care by first responders in an MCI or disaster.</p> <p>The information related to victims' information and triage time will be shared through SIGRUN.</p>
Premises and limitations	<p>The questionnaire will be answered by the responders involved in the UC 2 and 3.</p> <p>The data from SIGRUN will be checked in UC1, UC2 and UC3.</p> <p>Connectivity 4G between applications is required for the evaluation within SIGRUN. The connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform will be verified prior to the test. The terminals will be previously configured with the associated users.</p>
Security and Privacy Considerations	<p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the author is known to the institution to which he/she belongs.</p> <p>The permissions and users required for the test within SIGRUN will be enabled taking into account GRPD issues.</p> <p>The personal details of the victims used during UC exercise will be fictitious.</p>
Brief Description of the Test	<p>An MCI drill will be deployed, with defined roles and tasks: search & rescue, C2, EMS, security, etc., each of which generates data that are displayed and shared in real time. SIGRUN is used as the information exchange system. For the demo, various technological and software tools will be used to support responders, all of which are federated in SIGRUN.</p> <p>At the end of the simulation, the first responders answer the questionnaire anonymously. This questionnaire contains questions referring to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between services. • Extent to which the tested procedure would allow a more efficient execution of assigned tasks in a MCI compared to the current situation. • Opinion on whether this system would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to an MCI • Opinion on the ease and simplicity of implementation by a first responder in a MCI • Opinion on the improvement of the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in a MCI • Added value to the management and response in a MCI affecting several communities or countries • Overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged. • Degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.

The demonstration is complemented in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform: during the UC, relevant information will be gathered in order to carry out the proposed demonstrations.

Table 52 - Associated tests CO.WP5-13-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-13-D01

Harmonisation description: SIGRUN provides a common framework that allows emergency services to federate a set of interlinked capabilities to work together more effectively in UCs.

EM:

- Information exchange facilitation: The perceived improvement in information exchange between services using SIGRUN.
- Task execution efficiency: The perceived improvement in the efficiency of task execution in an MCI using SIGRUN compared to the current situation.
- Integration and cooperation: The perceived improvement in integration and cooperation with other services and/or procedures in responding to an MCI using SIGRUN.
- Implementation ease: The perceived ease and simplicity of implementing SIGRUN by first responders in an MCI.
- First responder well-being: The perceived improvement in the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in an MCI using SIGRUN.
- Added value in cross-border MCI management: The perceived added value of using SIGRUN for managing and responding to an MCI affecting several communities or countries.
- Satisfaction with information content: The overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged using SIGRUN.
- Satisfaction with the operational procedure: The degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.
- Accuracy of victim information: The extent to which the information of the victims shared through SIGRUN is accurate and reliable.
- Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.
- Triage accuracy: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.

MR:

- The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Accuracy of victim information: calculated by dividing the number of fully and correctly reported victims by the total number of reported victims, expressed as a percentage (%).• Time to triage: time from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions (in seconds).• Triage accuracy rate: calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage (%).
	KPI: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 4: Implementation ease: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 5: First responder well-being: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operational procedure: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.• KPI 9: Time to triage: Average time to assign primary triage priorities using SIGRUN: less than 1,5 min (90 sec).• KPI 10: Triage accuracy: Rate of at least 80% of correctly categorized victims during the MCI drill using SIGRUN.
	Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs. Rating spectrum: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs)• B: Very high adequacy (70-89%)• C: High adequacy (60-79%)• D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%)• E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 53 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-13-D01

Results sheet:

Result sheet will be provided in UC Report

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report.

5.8. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

Description: It has already been mentioned in section “CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response”, that deliverable D2.3/D2.8 includes the SIGRUN Minimum Data Set (MDS) to identify the entities used in the federation. One of the differentiated data sets in this respect is related to the incident.

The initial communication of an MCI or disaster and the information that is disseminated are essential to promote an efficient and effective emergency response from the beginning and throughout the evolution of the incident. Standardisation of the basic incident early warning information procedures will ensure that stakeholders receive consistent and clear information about the incident or hazards and the appropriate actions to be taken in response.

In their deliverable D5.4, the VALKYRIES experts have analysed the METHANE model, proposed in the UK by JESIP in its "Joint Doctrine: the interoperability framework", and concluded that it is an established information framework that provides a common structure for responders and their control centres to share incident information in a consistent, rapid and simple manner. The METHANE model was used as a reference for the development of SIGRUN and for the integration of the various related software tools used in the project demonstrators by the emergency services involved in the use cases (UCs).

Its validation was carried out by means of preliminary tests and in the UCs by means of specific surveys and demonstration within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform in a harmonized way.

5.8.1. CO.WP5-3 Verification by Test

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_2, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_BASE_T5.4_4, REQ_COM_T5.4_9, REQ_COM_T5.4_10, REQ_COM_T5.4_20, REQ_COM_T5.4_21, REQ_COM_T5.4_24, REQ_COM_T5.4_25

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-3-T01 - Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-3
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Test
Special Requirements	N/A

Test ID:	CO-WP5-3-T01 - Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: PRELIMINARY TEST
Information to collect	Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the initial information regarding the characteristics of the incident that is transmitted when a MCI or disaster is declared.
Pre-processing/Analysis	A questionnaire has been developed to collect information to assess whether the METHANE method is considered appropriate for the initial reporting of MCI. <i>M/ETHANE. Joint doctrine: the interoperability framework. Edition 2 July 2016. Pg 9.</i> https://www.jesip.org.uk/uploads/resources/JESIP-Joint-Doctrine.pdf
Premises and limitations	The questionnaire has been answered by first responders integrated in an EMS with professional experience.
Security and Privacy Considerations	The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.
Brief Description of the Test	<p>An MCI drill is carried out, organised by SUMMA 112 at the Instituto de Formación Integral en Seguridad y Emergencias (IFISE) in Madrid (Spain), with the participation of EMS personnel with experience in out-of-hospital care. During the rehearsal, the different links necessary for the activation and implementation of an incident response procedure are deployed, starting with the declaration of the incident. The METHANE methodology is used for this purpose. The first responder collects the information contained in this method to declare the incident, and this data is included in the system so that it can be shared by the different agencies. During the exercise, the data is updated if there is any change from the initial situation.</p> <p>At the end of the simulation, the first responders answer the questionnaire anonymously. This questionnaire includes questions on the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criticality of the information transmitted in the initial declaration of an MCI or disaster to increase the effectiveness of the health response and reduce the risk to responders. • Opinion on whether the information provided is appropriate to the needs of EMS in the early stages of a MCI or disaster.

Table 54 – Associated tests CO.WP5-3-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-3-T01	Harmonisation description: The M/ETHANE model is an established reporting framework that provides a common structure for responders and their control centres to share information about incidents. METHANE promotes the use of a common model, which means that information is shared
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	consistently, quickly and easily between emergency service providers and all actors involved in the response.
	EM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data relevance: Perceived importance of the data exchanged in the initial alert of a MCI or disaster to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response. Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the data exchanged during the drill in the initial alert to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.
	MR: The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).
	KPI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: Data relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. KPI 2: Data usefulness: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.
	Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs: A, Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% KPI 2: Data usefulness: 100,00% Rating spectrum: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs) B: Very high adequacy (70-89%) C: High adequacy (60-79%) D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%) E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)

Table 55 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-3-T01

Results sheet:

Result sheet will be provided in UC Report.

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report.

5.8.2. CO.WP5-12 Verification by Demo

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Demo

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP5-3
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Demonstration
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	<p>Information should be collected about the respondents' opinion on the initial information regarding the characteristics of the incident that is transmitted when a MCI or disaster is declared.</p> <p>The degree of compliance in the UCs execution with the METHANE model proposed by the VALKYRIES Project will also be checked in UC2.</p> <p><i>M/ETHANE. Joint doctrine: the interoperability framework. Edition 2 July 2016. Pg 9.</i></p> <p>https://www.jesip.org.uk/uploads/resources/JESIP-Joint-Doctrine.pdf</p>
Pre-processing/Analysis	<p>A questionnaire has been developed to collect information to assess whether the METHANE method is considered appropriate for the initial reporting of MCI.</p> <p>The data related to incident information sharing will be created and shared through SIGRUN to the C2 applications.</p>
Premises and limitations	<p>The questionnaire will be answered by the responders involved in the UC 2 and 3.</p> <p>The data from SIGRUN will also be reviewed in UC2. The evaluation within SIGRUN requires 4G connectivity between the applications. The connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform is checked before the test. The terminals are pre-configured with the associated users.</p>
Security and Privacy Considerations	<p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the author is known to the institution to which he/she belongs.</p> <p>The permissions and users required for the test within SIGRUN will be enabled taking into account GRPD issues.</p>
Brief Description of the Test	<p>An MCI drill will be deployed, with defined roles and tasks: search & rescue, C2, EMS, security, etc., each of which generates data that are displayed and shared in real time.</p> <p>SIGRUN is used as the information exchange system. For the demo, various technological and software tools will be used to support responders, all of which are federated in SIGRUN.</p> <p>At the end of the simulation, the first responders answer the questionnaire anonymously.</p> <p>At the end of the simulation, the first responders answer the questionnaire anonymously. This questionnaire includes questions on the following aspects:</p>

Test ID:	CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criticality of the information transmitted in the initial declaration of an MCI or disaster to increase the effectiveness of the health response and reduce the risk to responders. • Opinion on whether the information provided is appropriate to the needs of EMS in the early stages of an MCI or disaster. <p>The degree of compliance with the proposed METHANE model during the UCs will be assessed on the basis of the data recorded in SIGRUN during the conduct of each UC.</p>

Table 56 - Associated tests CO.WP5-3-12-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP5-3-D01	<p>Harmonisation description: The M/ETHANE is valid as a common model for sharing consistently, quickly and easily the incident information between emergency service providers and all actors involved in the UCs.</p> <p>EM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data relevance: Perceived importance of the data exchanged in the initial alert of a MCI or disaster to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response. • Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the data exchanged during the drill in the initial alert to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response. • METHANE UC compliance: The degree of adherence of the incident information shared in the UC to the METHANE model proposed by JOSIP. <p>MR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The answers to the questionnaires were expressed on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the most unfavourable result to the proposal (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) and 5 being the most favourable result (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED). • The METHANE UC compliance will be calculated by dividing the number of correctly shared METHANE data by the total METHANE dataset in the UC, expressed as a percentage (%). <p>KPI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 2: Data usefulness: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders. • KPI 3: METHANE UC compliance: A result of at least 80% of compliance. <p>Verification: Rating according to the total % compliance with the KPIs.</p> <p>Rating spectrum:</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A: Maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs)• B: Very high adequacy (70-89%)• C: High adequacy (60-79%)• D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59%)• E: Insufficient adequacy (<50%)
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Table 57 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP5-3-12-D01

Results sheet:

Result sheet will be provided in UC Report.

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence will be provided in UC Report.

6. WP6 - Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses harmonisation opportunities

6.1. CO.WP6.1: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

Description: This test refers to verifying that the data is correctly encrypted on the SGRUN platform.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Test

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T6.1_1

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test:

Test ID:	CO-WP6-1-T01 - Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO.WP6.1
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Analysis
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	N/A
Pre-processing/Analysis	Verify that data cannot be accessed when using cryptographic mechanisms.
Premises and limitations	The use of cryptographic mechanisms could not be suitable in situations where network coverage is extremely constrained. However, in most situations it could be applied.
Security and Privacy Considerations	All data exchanged must be protected using cryptography, except for specific situations, as described above.
Brief Description of the Test	Verify that the data transmitted over the network is secure applying cryptographic mechanisms to ensure that only authorized access can access it.

Table 58 – Associated tests CO.WP6.1-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP6-2-T01	Harmonisation description: The system MUST be able to store and transmit data in a secure way
	EM: Data transmitted over the network.
	MR: 100% of data transferred and stored in the SGRUN platform is encrypted, except for the cases defined in the premises and limitations
	KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Available = success) KPI 2: data transfer protocol configured to use encrypted communications: encryption setting KPI 3: data is stored with in an encrypted format: encryption setting
	Analysis: Analysis with the following valuation spectrum:

A: Successful verification. Data transmitted over the network is adequately managed from a cryptographic point of view.

Table 59 – Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP6.1-T01

Result sheet and evidence will be provided in UC Report.

6.2. CO-WP6-7- Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

Description: This test refers to verifying that if and how to put the data on the SIGRUN platform as well as how this data will be presented to the responders and C2.

Considerations: Incoming data will be fake (pre-prepared)

Verification Method: Inspection

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T6.5_1 (as one of the opportunities); REQ_COM_T6.5_3 (VOST is in many countries voluntary activity); REQ_COM_T6.5_4 (integration of VOST into the crisis management/response action system)

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: OBJ 13 (but partially also 7, 8, 9, 12)

Associated test

Test ID	CO-WP6-7-T01- Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO-WP6-7
Type	T3 – Functional tests
Qualification method	Inspection (I)
Special Requirements	Communication system (SIGRUN, iSafety,...) will be able to implement the message from VOST
Information to collect	3 possible messages as results of theoretical work of VOST in the form of e-mail (no specific data format), VOST is not directly connected to the C2 system
Preprocessing/Analysis	Pre-prepared messages from the fictive VOST will be sent to SIGRUN. The functionality and usage of such an information will be tested on the demonstrator and inspection of the result.
Premises and limitations	No VOST in Slovakia and UC2. The way how the information was created (work/procedure of VOST) is not in scope of this project.
Security and Privacy Considerations	It is assumed that the infrastructure involved complies with the relevant security and privacy policies. The resulting reports and information will be treated according to the contractually predefined levels of access and dissemination restrictions.
Brief Description of the Test	During the UC2 action, information from the VOST will appear on the communication platform. Incident commander should be able to reach this information and to use it for decision about next steps.

Test ID	CO-WP6-7-T01- Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)
	The result will be summarized within the debriefing discussion (possibly filling evaluation/validation form)

Table 60 - Associated tests CO.WP6.7-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP6-7-T01	Harmonisation description: the system should be able to receive the information and to present it to the responder
	EM: Information from VOST is included and available (visualized) in the communication platform.
	MR: Used to determine whether the system meets the performance harmonization opportunities needed to meet the EMs.
	KPI: Defined by stakeholders as measures of the minimum and critical performance of the system or process, as well as its level of acceptance.
	Verification: Inspection, with the following valuation spectrum: A: Successful verification. Use of VOST data is helpful and represent potential to significant response action improvement. B: Successful verification. Use of VOST data might play important role in response action management. The VOST data are not required – has no influence on the response action.

Table 61 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP6.7-T01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence of implementation will be integration of receiving of information coming from VOST in the form of e-mail message into the SIGRUN as well as presenting/visualization of this information.

Compliance of this opportunity will be discussed (verified) during the debriefing (in form of survey).

6.3. CO-WP6-11- Minimum Set of Competences and skills for volunteers and integration in the field Operational Procedures

Description: This harmonization opportunity focuses on defining a minimum set of competences and skills required for volunteers involved in first aid operations in disaster scenarios. The objective is to harmonize the required competencies to ensure the proper integration of volunteers in field operational procedures.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Inspection

Type: Non-functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T6.5_1, REQ_COM_T6.5_1, REQ_COM_T6.5_2, REQ_COM_T6.5_3, REQ_COM_T6.5_4

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-9, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-9, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-9, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-9

Associated test

Test ID	CO-WP6-11-D01- Minimum set of competences and skills for volunteers
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO-WP6-11
Type	Non-Functional tests
Qualification method	Inspection
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Feedback by all trainees (volunteers) on respective modules. Feedback by volunteers by Valkyries tools
Preprocessing/Analysis	Preliminary online training of the volunteers on using Valkyries tools
Premises and limitations	Full curricula and teaching content will not be tested in real-time during use cases implementations.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be collected and used in these tests.
Brief Description of the Test	The inspection will be conducted on the curriculum including modules for specific skills and knowledge that are necessary for the volunteers to contribute at first aid and personal safety in MCI. Recognize the emergency, activate an EMS system, and effective collaboration with other emergency actors.

Table 62 - Associated tests CO.WP6.11-D01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP6-11-D01	Harmonisation description: The course is expected to develop the knowledge and skills of the trainees in matters related to the fundamentals of CIMIC and the practical aspects of planning and managing activities in emergencies, crises and disasters of any nature.
	EM: Measures of mission success from the point of view of stakeholders. Positive feedback during the after-action review process.
	MR: Used to determine whether the system meets the performance harmonization opportunities needed to meet the EMs. NA E.g., Execution time (ms); resource consumption NA
	KPI: Defined by stakeholders as measures of the minimum and critical performance of the system or process, as well as its level of acceptance. NA E.g., Adequacy (%). Penalties in execution time (ms) and resource consumption (%). NA

	<p>Verification: Inspection/Demo, with the following valuation spectrum: demonstration of the training kit for first responders (curriculum and training content) during the UC2 and UC3; collecting feedback about the quality, content and methodology of the training.</p> <p>A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (the best possible performance was observed). E.g., No cost in execution time or resources.</p> <p>B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed. E.g., High adequacy (90%). Small cost in execution time or resources.</p> <p>C: Successful verification. The results are in line with expectations. Average approval. E.g., High adequacy (70%). Resource cost less than 50%.</p> <p>D: Successful verification. There is a wide range of improvements to be considered in future work. Conditionally approved. Minimum degree of approval. E.g., Sufficient adequacy (>50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.</p> <p>E: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded E.g., Insufficient adequacy (<50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.</p>
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Table 63 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP6.1-D01

Results sheet and evidence will be provided in UC Report

6.4. CO-WP6-10- Using Procedures and standard for Training and civil-military actions

Description This opportunity offers a set of knowledge and skills to the trainees in matters related to the fundamentals of CIMIC and the practical aspects of planning and managing activities with a view to improving coordination in emergencies, crises and disasters of any nature.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Inspection

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T6.4_1, REQ_COM_T6.4_1, REQ_COM_T6.4_2, REQ_COM_T6.4_3.

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-9.

Associated test

Test ID	CO-WP6-10-T01- Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO-WP6-10
Type	Validation by analyses
Qualification method	Inspection (I); feed-back questionnaire
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Feedback by all trainees (the military and civil from different agencies) on respective modules.
Preprocessing/Analysis	Advance online training of military and civilians to be familiar with the procedures and principles of the civil-military interaction.
Premises and limitations	Full curricula, methodology and learning content will be presented but not tested in real-time during use case implementations.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be collected and used in these tests.
Brief Description of the Test	The check will cover the curriculum, including modules on the specific knowledge and skills required by to build joint capabilities for civil-military interaction and coordination of efforts, which requires knowledge of the principles, rules, standards and procedures for such cooperation in a large-scale cross-border disaster with multiple casualties and destruction. Feedback from the experts and first responders will be collected conducted in the process of after-action review of UC3.

Table 64 - Associated tests CO.WP6.10-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP6-10-T01	Harmonisation description: This capability offers a set of knowledge and skills of the trainees in matters related to the fundamentals of CIMIC and the practical aspects of planning and managing activities in emergencies, crises and disasters of any nature.
	EM: Course information including curriculum, modules, methodology and feedback questionnaire are included and available (visualized) on the platform.
	MR: Compliance with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the content of the learning materials in the course and the expectations of the trainees.; - the content of the learning materials in the course and the expectations of the trainees; - adequacy of the presented materials and knowledge; - general satisfaction of the trainees with the acquired knowledge and skills.
	KPI 1: At least 80% covering the expectation.
	KPI 2: More than 90% of the learning materials in the course are adequately presented.
KPI 3: At least, 90% of the trainee's opinions are positive.	
Validation:	

	<p>The questionnaire contains questions referring to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Compliance of the provided knowledge and skills with the expectations of the trainees.- The degree of relevance of knowledge and competences.- Opinion on whether this course is practical oriented and would facilitate integration and joint work between military and other services in the response to an MCI.- Opinion on the teaching methodology and organization of the course.- Opinion which lectures and discussions are useful and why.- Added value to the crises management and overall rating for the course.- Overall satisfaction with the content of the course curriculum, methodology and learning content. <p>A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (the best possible performance was observed) and compliance of the knowledge and skills provided with the expectations of the trainees.</p> <p>B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed in the degree of relevance of knowledge and competences.</p> <p>C. Successful verification. High adequacy (90%) of practical orientation of the course.</p> <p>D: Successful verification. The results are in line with expectations about teaching methodology and organization of the course. Average approval (high adequacy (70%)) of the lectures and discussions.</p> <p>E: Successful verification. There is a wide range of improvements to be considered in future work. Conditionally approved. Minimum degree of approval. Sufficient adequacy (>50%). Possible issues for improvement in execution time and resources.</p> <p>F: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded. Insufficient adequacy (<50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.</p>
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Table 65 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP6.10-T01

Results sheets and evidence will be provided in the UC Report.

6.5. CO.WP6.5- Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)

Description: This test is associated with the harmonisation opportunity including education and training for first aid responses. It defines process of inspection of the Training kit containing

curriculum, methodology, and training manual that have been developed to validate this opportunity at the European level.

Considerations: N/A

Verification Method: Inspection

Type: Functional

Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T6.2_1, REQ_BASE_T6.2_2, REQ_BASE_T6.2_3, REQ_BASE_T6.2_4, REQ_COM_T6.2_1, REQ_COM_T6.2_2, REQ_COM_T6.2_3, REQ_COM_T6.2_4, REQ_COM_T6.2_5

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5

Associated test

Test ID	CO-WP6-5-T01-Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)
Level	Harmonization Opportunity CO-WP6 .5
Type	Validation by analysis, demonstration and feed-back questionnaire
Qualification method	Inspection (I)
Special Requirements	N/A
Information to collect	Feedback by all trainees (the first responders) on respective curriculum and modules. Feedback by all trainees on the VALKYRIES tools: INDRA: iSafety Application Modules for C2; PARTICLE's Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP); TASSICA 3 Triage card;
Preprocessing/Analysis	Preliminary online training of the first responders on using VALKYRIES tools. Onsite training of first responders during UC3.
Premises and limitations	Full curricula and teaching content will be presented and tested in real-time during UC3 execution.
Security and Privacy Considerations	No personal data will be collected and used in these tests.
Brief Description of the Test	The inspection will be on the curriculum including modules for specific skills and knowledge that are necessary for the individual to provide first aid with a limited amount of equipment; recognize the emergency, activate an EMS system, and serve as the liaison with other emergency services, fire brigade, military, and police. Feedback from the first responders will be collected conducted in tin the process of an after-action review action UC3.

Table 66 - Associated tests CO.WP6.5-T01

Criteria for assessing compliance:

CO-WP6-5-T01	The Training kit must enhance the work of first responders in case of cross-border MCI by providing knowledge and skills in several key areas. First, awareness of emergency conditions and/or the proper extent of injuries which require first aid. Second, ability to administer appropriate first aid for life threatening injuries (relative to airway, breathing and circulation). Third, evacuation/transport of the victim to medical care facility. Fourth, assist health care providers. Fourth, use of modern digital tools for triage, enhanced situational awareness, data management and protection, communication and information exchange, etc.
	EM: Positive feedback during the after-action review process
	MR: Used to determine whether the system meets the performance harmonization opportunities needed to meet the EMs. E.g., Execution time (ms); resource consumption (memory, CPU. NA
	KPI: Defined by stakeholders as measures of the minimum and critical performance of the system or process, as well as its level of acceptance. E.g., Adequacy (%). Penalties in execution time (ms) and resource consumption (%). NA
	Validation: Inspection/Analysis/Test/Demo, with the following valuation spectrum: demonstration of the training kit for first responders (curriculum and training content) during the UC3; collecting feedback about the quality, content and methodology of the training.
	<p>A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (the best possible performance was observed). E.g., No cost in execution time or resources.</p> <p>B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed. E.g., High adequacy (90%). Small cost in execution time or resources.</p> <p>C: Successful verification. The results are in line with expectations. Average approval. E.g., High adequacy (70%). Resource cost less than 50%.</p> <p>D: Successful verification. There is a wide range of improvements to be considered in future work. Conditionally approved. Minimum degree of approval. E.g., Sufficient adequacy (>50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.</p> <p>E: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded E.g., Insufficient adequacy (<50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.</p>

Table 67 - Criteria for assessing compliance CO.WP6.5-T01

Results sheets and evidence will be provided in UC Report

7. Conclusions

In the scope of the Technological Opportunities for WP4, one of the most complex challenges was presented at the verification stage, focusing on the preparation of the data models in the SIGRUN environment, as well as on the command-and-control tools. Requiring the synchronisation and joint testing of these tools in the framework of the SIGRUN interoperability model was a significant effort, essential to ensure the correct functioning of the integrations.

In the process of developing each use case, the preparation of static data encompassing both organisations and assets was imperative, along with the extensive testing of dynamic data, which included mission simulation and the assignment of assets to each mission. It should be noted that iSafety already had a pre-existing data model for Organisations/Assets, which was adapted and adjusted to the SIGRUN reference structure. Compared to past experiences, such as the integration with the EDXL-CAP protocol, this process was more efficient, being facilitated by the inherent configurability of the application used, designed with that purpose in mind.

A critical aspect that should not be overlooked is ensuring optimal communication coverage. The success of the project depends to a large extent on ensuring that communications between the different tools and systems involved are complete and effective. In this regard, testing plays an essential role in verifying the smooth operation of the system. However, in emergency situations, it becomes imperative to have contingency plans (Plan B or even Plan C) that can be activated in case circumstances require an alternative response.

The verification process of the WP5 specific enablers proposed for harmonisation and standardisation in deliverable D5.4 is carried out in 2 phases:

1. PRELIMINARY TESTING: to finalise the design and implementation of the proposed enablers as required.
2. DEMONSTRATIONS: to demonstrate the results of the proposed enablers in the context of cross-border MCIs or disasters.

A total of 7 enablers corresponding to 6 different harmonisation opportunities have been tested in relation to WP5.

One of the most complex aspects in the testing and validation process of the proposed WP5 solutions has been related to the operational procedures for MCI or disaster response deployed in the demonstrators. A review of the specific operational procedures of each agency involved, UC by UC, has been necessary to identify in each case the best way to integrate the VALKYRIES proposals into these procedures.

In the process of defining these "new" operational procedures, a number of premises have been taken into account:

- The defined procedure must be rigorous: it must conform to the reality of professional practice in these circumstances, to scientific evidence, etc.
- It must be valid for all the circumstances that may potentially arise in the UC, so as not to compromise the development or outcome of the same.
- It should involve as little variation as possible with respect to the usual operating procedure of each service, in order to favour its learning and effective implementation. At the same time, this will allow the variations found in the evaluation to be focused on the enablers introduced.

The training process for the responders was also the result of intense debate and work by the project's researchers. For the UCs, we have worked with professional responders who, in addition to their dedication to the preparation and execution of the demonstrators, have logically had to continue to attend to their usual professional obligations. This has obliged VALKYRIES researchers to try their best to optimise the time and effort additionally demanded from these professionals for the specific objectives of the project. This has been achieved through a combination of:

- Resources for autonomous, delocalised and asynchronous learning through tutorials specifically designed for this purpose and made available to all those involved in the UCs.
- Specific face-to-face trainings to acquire the specific practical skills required.

A fundamental aspect has also been the design of the tests and demonstrators to allow the comparison of the different proposals and the evaluation of the specific VALKYRIES proposals. And within these, especially the organisation and execution of the data recording in the exercises developed outside the SIGRUN integration, i.e., without automatic data capture (this is the case for example of the reference exercises developed with the usual operational procedures or with the use of the TASSICA 3 card). A factor that exemplifies this is the coincidence of multiple agencies from multiple countries, with multiple responders working simultaneously in different languages and with different operational procedures: determining the number, location and characteristics of observers and evaluators has required an effective reconciliation between the need to collect the information on the one hand, and the real possibilities of the Project on the other.

In the context of WP6, verification and validation of the prioritised harmonisation opportunities were carried out also in two phases. A total of five harmonization opportunities have been tested and verified. The opportunity related to cryptographic mechanisms for data protection was validated in the framework of WP4, as a part of the integrated VALKYRIES system's functions. The other four harmonization opportunities underwent verification and validation activities in WP6.

The first phase was the verification stage, conducted during the preliminary phase of Use Case 3. It involved two cycles during the development of standardised courses and common procedures for education and training of first aid responders, volunteers, civil-military cooperation actions, and the use of Virtual Operation Support Teams.

During two workshops held in Bulgaria, sets of training kits were presented, discussed, and pre-tested. The workshops' discussions resulted in the refinement and development of content, guidelines, and main topics for the education and practical training of various first responders in the event of multi-casualty and cross-border incident responses. The primary focus was on harmonizing diverse procedures and practices across participating member states (consortium partners) to derive common principles for education, cross-border cooperation, and collaboration.

The second phase of the testing of WP6 harmonisation opportunities took place during the Use Case 3 demonstrations, which represented the validation phase. The course contents for the four harmonization opportunities were presented to stakeholders and first responders. Additionally, training sessions were conducted to practice the shared educational content

provided in the joint multinational and multidisciplinary training kits. The VALKYRIES solutions and training received highly positive evaluations from participating first responders. They gave very good and excellent ratings for the relevance of knowledge, the logical connection between individual components, teaching methodology, and course organization.

First, during UC3 execution, CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures was demonstrated and tested. Besides, CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions was also tested with military cadets from the Bulgarian National Defence University. The contents, methodology and lecture materials were presented, which were very well received by the training participants. As a result of the discussions, the main characteristics of Operational Manual CIMIC In Emergencies were outlined, such as the content, guidelines and main topics related to practical training, the principles and approaches that should be followed to improve civil-military interaction in natural disasters accompanied by mass casualties. The benefit of such a document at national and European level was confirmed by the participants. The overall evaluation of the course is more than positive - very good and excellent rates for relevance of knowledge, logical connection between individual parts, teaching methodology and organization of the course. Some parts of the curriculum, such as the duration of the duration practical orientation of the knowledge and skills could be put under consideration. As a whole, very positive appreciation allows to consider that it successfully passes the testing and validation at this stage.

Moreover, during UC3 implementation the CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid response was demonstrated and tested. This opportunity was demonstrated and validated through presentations and training sessions of the stakeholders just before the real UC3 execution. One whole day was devoted to presenting the VALKYRIES tools and the content of the Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training kit. The feedback data using online questionnaire from participants was collected during the debriefing day after UC3 execution in order to analyse the end users' assessments and their satisfaction with the content/curriculum teaching methodology and training materials for first responders. The participating first responders evaluated the training very positively.

The critical aspect of all courses and training proposed by VALKYRIES is the harmonization of existing educational principles and procedures across different countries, aiming to offer joint multinational content and curriculum.

Finally, during UC2 execution the CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) was demonstrated and tested. This opportunity was focused on incorporation of information, which VOST was producing into the information flow of the first responders. The focus was given on how the information coming from VOST could be presented to C2 post, to Incident Commander and other related actors. Testing of this opportunity was presented to all involved within UC2 during preparation phase the day before UC2 SK-IT exercise execution. The overall evaluation of this harmonization opportunity was done through inspection and in the form of survey. Verification was successful – use of data from VOST is for first responders helpful and contributes to improvement during response action, data gathered from VOST can be important within response action management, but on the other hand data are not required – has no influence on the response action and on decision making process. The result from the survey

shows that for involved responders, information from VOST represents potential to improve response action on strategic and tactical level, as well as on operational.

8. Bibliography

8.1. Internal references

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3. **Consortium VALKYRIES.** Deliverable D2.8, "Architecture Design Document". 2022.
4. **Consortium VALKYRIES.** Deliverable D2.7. "Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases"
5. **Consortium VALKYRIES.** Deliverable D7.1. "Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology"
6. **Consortium VALKYRIES.** Deliverable D7.4. "Reference Integration and Lessons Learned Report"
7. **Consortium VALKYRIES.** Deliverable D5.4. "Valkyries harmonization's on first aid response common practices and procedures"

9. ANNEX A – Glossary

Acronym	Description
COP	Common Operational Picture
CPU	Central Processing Unit
EM	Effectiveness measures
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EU	European Union
EUR-ERP	EU Emergency Response Plans
FR	First Responder
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
Health ITUES	Health Information Technology Usability and Usefulness Evaluation Scale
HO	Harmonisation Opportunity
HTL	Hybrid Twin Lab
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
ID	Identification
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MCI	Multi-Casualty Incident
METHANE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major Incident Declared • Exact location • Type of incident • Hazards • Access • Number and type of casualties • Emergency services present and required
MR	Performance Measures
N/A	Not Applicable
ToC	Table of Content
TBD	To Be Defined
TBR	To Be Reviewed
UC	Use Case
VCMS	Victims Case Management System
VMI	Virtual Machine Interface

Table 68 – Glossary

10. ANNEX B – Template for harmonization verification

The general template used for the harmonisation opportunity verification is the following:

Description: <TBD>

Considerations: <TBD>

Verification Method: <Inspection/Analysis/Test/Demo>

Type (if the Verification Method is a Test): <Functional/ Non-functional>

Traceability with identified requirements: <>

Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives:<>

Priority: <P1/P2/P3>

Associated test:

Test ID:	HO-5-X-Title
Level	Harmonization Opportunity 1
Type	<i>E.g., T3 – Functional tests</i>
Qualification method	<i>E.g., Analysis(A)</i>
Special Requirements	<i>E.g., N/A</i>
Information to collect	<i>E.g., Interfaces, data models, limitations of the technological deployment environment.</i>
Preprocessing/Analysis	<i>E.g., Execution of the functionality on the demonstrator and inspection of the result.</i>
Premises and limitations	<i>E.g., Limitations related to the capabilities of the virtualization platform on which the demonstrator is deployed.</i>
Security and Privacy Considerations	<i>E.g., It is assumed that the infrastructure involved complies with the relevant security and privacy policies. The resulting reports and information will be treated according to the contractually predefined levels of access and dissemination restrictions.</i>
Brief Description of the Test	<i>E.g., On the deployed demonstrator, test the possibility of configuration and networks. Check the result on the virtualized scenario. The result will be a calculation of the percentage of possible flexibility in configuration. In a complementary way, the number of resources consumed during the execution of the test battery will be tested, as well as its execution time.</i>

Table 69 - Associated test template

Criteria for assessing compliance:

HO-5-X-Title	Harmonisation description:
	EM: Measures of mission success from the point of view of stakeholders.
	MR: Used to determine whether the system meets the performance harmonization opportunities needed to meet the EMs. E.g., Execution time (ms); resource consumption (memory, CPU).
	KPI: Defined by stakeholders as measures of the minimum and critical performance of the system or process, as well as its level of acceptance. E.g., Adequacy (%). Penalties in execution time (ms) and resource consumption (%).
	Verification Inspection/Analysis/Test/Demo, with the following valuation spectrum:
	A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (the best possible performance was observed). E.g., No cost in execution time or resources.
	B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed. E.g., High adequacy (90%). Small cost in execution time or resources.
	C: Successful verification. The results are in line with expectations. Average approval. E.g., High adequacy (70%). Resource cost less than 50%.
	D: Successful verification. There is a wide range of improvements to be considered in future work. Conditionally approved. Minimum degree of approval. E.g., Sufficient adequacy (>50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.
	E: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded E.g., Insufficient adequacy (<50%). Possible penalties in execution time and resources.

Table 70 – Criteria for assessing compliance template

Results sheet:

Harmonisation Opportunity #ID to verify			
Description	<i>Scope and coverage of the harmonisation opportunity (HO)</i>		
Traceability	<i>Traceability of the HO with respect to the tests carried out</i>		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
<i>Error rate (%), etc.</i>	<i>Milliseconds, CPU usage (%)</i>	<i>False positives, accuracy, variability, etc...</i>	<i>Inspection, analysis, etc.</i>
Verification action #1	Description	<i>Description of the action and its context. It includes premises, expected results, etc.</i>	
	Execution	<i>Step-by-step description of how the verification test was run.</i>	
	Analysis and results	<i>Description of the procedure for collecting results, its analytical actions (if necessary) and the general results achieved.</i>	
	History of corrective measures	<i>If the verification initially failed, this cell describes the different corrective actions to fit expectations.</i>	
	Lessons learned	<i>It highlights the difficulties suffered, and any possible conclusions or lessons learned to be considered in the later stages of development.</i>	
	Quality	<i>Functional score of the verification action [A, B, C, D, E]. The legend of the score varies depending on the element to be validated, being declared for each test along with the quality thresholds to be considered.</i>	
	End-user feedback	<i>Any comments highlighted by the end users of the Project during the verification process.</i>	
	Result	<i>YES/NO. Did you pass the test successfully? The achievement criteria require compliance with the verification (Quality Rating) and validation (Acceptance) criteria in accordance with the thresholds indicated.</i>	
Verification Action #2			
			...
verification action #n			

Table 71 – Results sheet template

11. ANNEX F – Use Case common opportunities

11.1. Matrix UC opportunities tools

		UC				TOOLS								
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	iSafety	SIGRUN	Tassica Cards	Global COP	Simulation tools	Application for digitalizing triage	TAP2SOS	Blockchain module	HTL
WP4	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	X		X	X		X		X	X				
	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace		X	X	X		X							
	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X			X
	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage				X							X		
	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	X	X	X			X							
	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs				X		X							

Table 72 - Matrix UC opportunities tools WP4

		UC				TOOLS								
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	iSafety	SIGRUN	Tassica Cards	Global COP	Simulation Tools	Application for digitalizing triage	TAP2SOS	Blockchain module	HTL
WP5	CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response	X	X	X	X			X						
	CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response	X	X	X		X	X		X		X			
	CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response		X	X			X		X		X			
	CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response		X	X			X							
	CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans	X							X					
	CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response		X	X			X				X			

Table 73 - Matrix UC opportunities tools WP5

		UC				TOOLS								
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	iSafety	SIGRUN	Tassica Cards	Global COP	Simulation Tools	Application for digitalizing triage	TAP2SOS	Blockchain module	HTL
WP6	CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	X	X	X			X							
	CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)		X											
	CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.			X										
	CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions			X										
	CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).			X										

Table 74 - Matrix UC opportunities tools WP6

11.2. Valkyries integrated system

11.2.1. SIGRUN

The SIGRUN Framework reference implementation implements the architecture and model defined in D2.8, as the backbone information distribution and services orchestration that enables the functional interoperability between the End-user applications, as a federation of tools.

Within each UC demo the reference framework implementation was slightly improved to correct some issues detected in the previous demonstrations and tests or to add new functions to improve its functionality and performance.

For each UC demo an independent database and uses were created in order to separate each results and tests.

11.2.2. GLOBAL COP

The Global COP provides a Dynamic situational awareness of the resources and a data sharing tool between the national / supranational command posts.

The GLOBAL COP displayed to each of the Command posts and decision-maker the ground information reported by the actors (First responders / Victims / assets geographical position and his status). Multiple instances of the GLOBAL COP were used, each one displaying its country data as well as the data that was shared by the other nation.

The GLOBAL COP also was tested against the victim's historical data as report by the triage process and by the decision makers for its displacement to the medical response units.

GLOBAL COP displayed the correct position, and the response structure as defined by the command organization, the forces and units involved, their assets, including its status and characteristics.

The GLOBAL_COP provides multiple views of the filed actors, assets and their status.

Global View:

Figure 1 - Global COP main view

Assets View:

Figure 2 - Global COP assets view

Victims List View:

Label	Last Updated	Gender	Age / Age Group	Assistance Status	AT	ET	Main Pathology	Transport	Destination	Location	Triage History	Incident	By Unit	By Staff
TASS0022 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:37	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK		AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd ERMK - Special Unit for disasters	FSD_Gr_1033
TASS0031 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:24	M	32 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA (abdomen/belly)	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0015 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:29	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK		PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0035 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:24	M	56 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0018 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:24	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK		AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0011 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:14	M	17 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd ERMK - Special Unit for disasters	FSD_Gr_1033
TASS0049 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:24	M	60 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA (head/neck)	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd ERMK - Special Unit for disasters	FSD_Gr_1033
TASS0040 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:29	M	30 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0056 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:14	M	- / ELDER	Completed	OK	OK				+	+	Flood		HST1 1311
TASS0010 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:22	M	20 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA	PARTICLE AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd ERMK - Special Unit for disasters	FSD_Gr_1033
TASS0065 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:13	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK				+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0019 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:21	M	25 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA (head/neck)	AMBULANCE	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0014 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:19	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK				+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0090 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:23	M	26 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA (lower extremity)	RNU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Flood		HST1 1311
TASS0081 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:22	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK				+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0012 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:18	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK		RNU - AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0070 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:14	M	40 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA (head/neck)	HOSPITAL AMBULANCE 1	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd ERMK - Special Unit for disasters	FSD_Gr_1033
TASS0048 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:09	M	17 / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK	TRAUMA	RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Flood		HST1 1311
TASS0017 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:07	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK				+	+	Earthquake Greece		FSD_Bulk_1022
TASS0062 II	Nov 14, 2023, 19:27	M	- / ADULT	Completed	OK	OK		RNU - AMBULANCE 2	St. Vlach HOSPITAL	+	+	Earthquake Greece	2nd ERMK - Special Unit for disasters	FSD_Gr_1033

Figure 3 - Global COP Victims List View

Incident Victims' status View

Figure 4 - Global COP Incident Victims' status View

11.2.3. iSafety

iSafety is an Integrated Incident & Emergency Management System with different modules to deploy Call Receiving, Incident Dispatch and Tracking, Radio/Voice communications integration and Reports, based on Geographic Information System (GIS) and Vehicle Location (AVL).

For each Use Case iSafety was pre-configured with the data of the agencies and assets participating in the project and the following iSafety functionalities were integrated into SIGRUN: Incident creation, Mission/Tasks Creation, Assignment of vehicles to missions, Updating vehicles status data (in progress, at the incident site, free). All these data was shared to SIGRUN and displayed in the GLOBAL COP.

For each UC the type of missions/tasks are also adjusted to fit into the common SIGRUN model for all UC.

11.2.4. iSafety Implementation for the UC

The functionalities implemented in iSafety for adaptation to the SIGRUN reference model for all UCs are described below.

ISAFETY ENVIRONMENT FOR DRILL

KEY POINTS

- iSafety is a Command and Control Application **web based**.
- iSafety will work **in parallel** with the actual tools in the drill.
- It will be used as a tool in the **mobile command and control** center.
- **A tablet** can also be deployed to complement with data at the incident site.
- iSafety allows **operation in offline mode** and subsequent synchronization with the control Center.
- For the simulation, iSafety will **send and receive** data from the SGRUN platform.
- Can be configured in **multi-agency or single-agency** mode
- **Customized Operational dashboards** are available

Figure 5 - iSafety key points

ISAFETY CYCLE TREATMENT- STEP 1- INCIDENT CREATION

STEP 1- Incident Creation (112)

The event will be created in 112 and the event will be duplicated in iSafety.

The incident indicates the type of event and the Geolocation. iSafety will report the incident to SGRUN.

Letter of receipt of call

- Incident classification (fire, explosion)
- Geolocation
- SOP
- Agencies involved

It is possible to integrate with 112 or create the incident manually.

Figure 6 - iSafety Incident creation

ISAFETY CYCLE TREATMENT- STEP 2- INCIDENT DISPATCHING

- **STEP 2- Incident Dispatching (112)**
- The resources dedicated to the incident are indicated here (ambulances, drones...). The operator sees the available resources and the system proposes a resource dispatch according to the incident category. A previous allocation may have been made in 112.

DECISION MAKING HELP

Figure 7 - iSafety Incident dispatching

ISAFETY CYCLE TREATMENT- STEP 3- INCIDENT TRACKING

- **STEP 3- Incident Tracking (MC2)**
- At this point the operator manually updates the resource information (location and status of ambulances or vehicles) if there is no possible integration. It registers affected entities (injured, buildings) and reports the information as a log for the rest of the users connected to the event.

The application keeps a record of the interactions between users (right side)

Figure 8 - iSafety Incident Tracking

ISAFETY CYCLE TREATMENT- STEP 4- GIS MONITOR

- **STEP 4- GIS Monitor (MC2)**
Throughout the incident, the map appears with real time information which the localization and state of the resources (ambulances, drones, deployed vehicles)

Common Operational Picture

Figure 9 - iSafety GIS Monitor

ISAFETY CYCLE TREATMENT- STEP 4- TACTICAL MAPS

Tactical maps can be edited with geographical information about the incident and meeting points. This information is published for all Operators/Agencys

Figure 10 - iSafety Tactical Maps

ISAFETY CYCLE TREATMENT- STEP 5- DASHBOARDS

Unidad	Clase	Nombre	Tip	Grupo de control	Nivel de emergencia	CO2/100	Estado
43GRUPO	8223	8223	Autobombas CL 210 T	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
BHELEME	1022	1022	Helicopteros EC 130 (R4) 200	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
43GRUPO	8224	8224	Autobombas CL 415	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
BHELEME	1025	1025	Helicopteros EC 130 (R4) 200	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
43GRUPO	8225	8225	Autobombas CL 415	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
43GRUPO	8226	8226	Autobombas CL 415	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
BHELEME	1023	1023	Helicopteros EC 130 (R4) 200	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
43GRUPO	8223	8223	Autobombas CL 210 T	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
BHELEME	1012	1012	Helicopteros EC 130 (R4) 200	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	No disponible
CEM41	AU 32	Autobomba 32	Autobomba LRO BP 40-106 F 1004	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	Disponible
UNIM/CGJ	1111	Estación Merida		GALEME	Nivel 5	-	Disponible
CEM41	413	413LEON	León	GALEME	Nivel 3	-	Disponible
BRU6	BRU2	ESTACIÓN TORREJÓN		GALEME	Nivel 5	-	Disponible
CEM42	LE 09	LEON 09	León	GALEME	Nivel 4	-	Disponible
CEM41	38 213	38ANANJAS 213	ESTACIÓN 38ANANJAS	GALEME	Nivel 3	-	Disponible
BRU6	BRU5	BRU5	ESTACIÓN VIGO	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	Disponible
BRU6H11	1127	BRU6	BRU6	GALEME	Nivel 3	-	Disponible
BRU6H11	HE 196	HE 196	Estación Merida	GALEME	Nivel 3	-	Disponible
BHELEME	H224	H224	Helicopteros EC 130 (R4) 200	GALEME	Nivel 5	-	Activo

Real time information about the resources Available/ Not available/ On the way

Figure 11 - iSafety Dashboards

11.2.5. TASSICA triage card

VALKYRIES support a standardised triage card, TASSICA 3, to be used by emergency services likely to be involved in a mass casualty incident to ensure interoperability between services (professional or volunteer, civilian or military), fairness in the prioritisation of treatment, recording of casualty information and traceability in mass casualty incidents and disasters.

It is resistant to liquids (water, blood, grease, NBC decontamination), tear-resistant. It can be used with all common writing media (biros, felt-tip pen, pencil). It is easy to attach to the patient by means of a lanyard (adjustable strap). It would be used at the scene of the incident by EMS FRs from both sides of the border.

The objective is to verify that (in addition to allowing individual victim identification by means of a unique ID code and allowing the victim's priority to be labelled like any triage card):

- It helps EMS FR through the victim healthcare process on the MCI scene.
- It unifies criteria and quality in the response of FR EMS to MCI.
- It ensures clinical information and patient traceability: a clinical report always accompanies the victim, and also leaves a written record of the patient's information at each link in the care chain. This includes victims who start being assisted by FR EMS from one country and end up being assisted or evacuated by FR EMS from the other country.

Its use aims to establish common elements between different ways to work, thus promoting homogenisation and interoperability, in relation to the following operating procedures

- Primary triage (determining and labelling the priority of each victim to be treated on-site).
- Application of immediate life-saving care actions.
- Patient assessment (primary and secondary) and stabilisation.
- Secondary triage (determining and labelling the priority for evacuation).

- Evacuation
- Recording clinical information and patient traceability.
- Recording the first responder's healthcare activities at the scene

Figure 12 - TASSICA triage card

11.2.6. Application for digitalizing triage process

The applications for digitalizing triage process runs on multiple devices (smartphone, tablets), for health workers in the IMV. It can be used on-site by the health workers to raise alert and report about the characteristics and evolution of the accident victims in real time, as well as to support and communicate in real time the triage process of the victims. This application would allow the First Responders to perform their work responding to MCI or disasters.

It helps to demonstrate the benefits of the VALKYRIES proposals in terms of

- Harmonisation of terms and criteria between different health services.
- Supporting the decision making of the emergency services.
- Capture the victims' information in real time without increasing the workload of the EMS.
- Share information in real time between and with other entities through SIGRUN, improving patient traceability, follow-up and decision making.
- Allow victims and FRs to be located and tracked in real time (via SIGRUN) without disrupting care work.
- Reduce EMS voice communications, both upstream and downstream

The testing of this tool was performed in parallel with the triage process, (described above in sub-chapter 9.4). It is important to state that the application for digitalizing triage process was integrated with SIGRUN and related tools.

11.2.7. TASSICA TB bracelets

TASSICA TB bracelets are LED wearable devices made of waterproof material designed to be attached to each victim in an MCI or disaster (whether uninjured or injured) with a dual function:

- To assign a unique ID to each victim, allowing their individual identification, registration and tracking (e.g. in SIGRUN and federated applications). This ID is displayed on the surface of the wearable in 2 ways: in the form of an alphanumeric code (allowing it to be read at a glance) and in the form of the equivalent QR (allowing the ID to be read quickly and accurately by the appropriate devices).
- Triage priority labelling: each TASSICA TB bracelet can light up (LED) in each of the 5 colours of the pentapolar code proposed by VALKYRIES as a standard for the priority marking of victims in MCI or disasters. The wristband can change colour at any time to adapt to variations in the priority assigned to the victim in question. The activation or colour change of the wristband can be done manually (directly by the first responder) or automatically (possible at the current stage of development via DMX protocol). In the VALKYRIES demonstrators, manual activation/colour change option was used due to the specific characteristics and conditions of the project.

In the demonstrators where the bracelets were employed, they were used in combination with the application for digitalizing triage process, being the TASSICA TB ID managed in this app as internal ID, and in SIGRUN as the external ID of each victim.

Figure 13 - bracelets for triage

11.2.8. Blockchain logging module

Blockchain logging of all transactions and metadata exchanged through SIGRUN.

The blockchain module of SIGRUN developed by BC2050, had been tested stand alone as per its functionality, logging encrypted data on a private Blockchain network following the Ethereum standards. Such tests were performed also during this UC using third party tools such as:

1. **Geth:** set up and test the Ethereum client
2. **Node.js, npm:** runtime environment and package manager
3. **Truffle Suite:** deploy and test smart contracts
4. **Web3.js:** interact with Ethereum nodes
5. **Git:** version control
6. **Remix:** deploy and debug smart contracts

The private blockchain network was deployed using Raspberry Pis running all needed Ethereum protocols and algorithms.

Figure 14 – Blockchain login module

In this UC test, the module was attached in SIGRUN using PARTICLE's APP.

```
Contract: VPPAuction
Contract Deployment
Contract Address: 0xE6a8CE2d1Ccd1c32be4b7EF6c3e1b3195A11495b
  ✓ Should Deploy Successfully
Auction Creation
  ✓ Should create a new auction (915ms)
Placing Bids
  ✓ Should place a valid bid (673ms)
  ✓ Should reject a lower bid (178ms)
  ✓ Should accept a higher bid (648ms)
  ✓ Should reject a bid with the same amount as the highest bid (122ms)
  ✓ Should reject a bid from the auction's seller (105ms)
  ✓ Should reject bid after auction end time and refund bidder1 (15112ms)
Seller calls endAuction after time passed:
  ✓ Should end the auction and transfer the highest bid to the seller (2382ms)
  ✓ Should reject ending the auction twice (133ms)
Events Emitted
  ✓ Should emit AuctionStarted event when auction is created (1114ms)
  ✓ Should emit HighestBidIncreased event when a valid bid is placed (628ms)
  ✓ Should emit AuctionEnded event when the auction is ended (7082ms)
Edge Cases
  ✓ Should accept a very high bid (715ms)
  ✓ Should reject a very low bid (103ms)
  ✓ Should reject a bid placed at the exact same time as the auction's end time (5117ms)
Multiple Sellers and Buyers
  ✓ Should allow multiple sellers to create auctions (306ms)
  ✓ Should allow multiple buyers to place bids on different auctions (1687ms)
Simultaneous Auctions with Different End Times
  ✓ Should allow bids on both auctions while they are active (2045ms)
  ✓ Should reject bids on the first auction after it ends, while the second auction is still active (10944ms)
  ✓ Should reject bids on both auctions after they have ended (10250ms)
  ✓ Should allow ending both auctions separately after their respective end times (7429ms)
Contract: VPPLogging
  ✓ should record energy transaction that also acts as a certificate (838ms)
  ✓ should fetch EnergyTransaction by the initial issuer (2490ms)
  ✓ should revert if non-owner tries to fetch energy transaction (1606ms)
  ✓ should return energy transactions by owner (1578ms)
  ✓ should return all energy transactions (2833ms)

27 passing (1m)
```

Figure 15 - Transactions SIGRUN BLC

Transactions and data/metadata exchanged through SIGRUN were logged smoothly with no loss of information or duplicates, causing no significant load to the systems employed in the integration tests before this UC execution.


```

root@node1-desktop: /home/node1/nodetest
INFO [06-26]11:57:55.964 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:57:55.959 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:57:55.973 * mined potential block
WARN [06-26]11:58:01.211 Snapshot extension registration failed
INFO [06-26]11:58:02.045 Looking for peers
INFO [06-26]11:58:02.743 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:58:02.744 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:58:02.744 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:58:02.745 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:02.746 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:03.497 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:58:03.498 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:58:03.498 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:58:03.499 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:03.499 Commit new sealing work
WARN [06-26]11:58:05.158 Snapshot extension registration failed
INFO [06-26]11:58:07.768 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:58:07.769 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:58:07.769 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:58:07.771 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:07.773 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:13.304 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:58:13.307 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:13.312 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:13.314 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:13.318 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:58:17.193 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:58:17.194 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:58:17.194 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:58:17.194 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:17.248 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:22.092 Looking for peers
INFO [06-26]11:58:24.192 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:58:24.193 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:58:24.193 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:58:24.195 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:25.915 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:58:25.915 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:58:25.915 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:58:25.916 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:32.218 Looking for peers
INFO [06-26]11:58:42.266 Looking for peers
INFO [06-26]11:58:46.057 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:58:46.058 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:58:46.061 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:46.062 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:58:52.353 Looking for peers
INFO [06-26]11:59:01.452 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:59:01.453 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:59:01.453 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:59:01.466 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:59:01.467 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:59:02.378 Looking for peers
INFO [06-26]11:59:07.478 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:59:07.479 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:59:07.479 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:59:07.479 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:59:07.481 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:59:10.179 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:59:10.192 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:59:10.203 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:59:10.270 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:59:10.271 * mined potential block*
INFO [06-26]11:59:12.429 Looking for peers
INFO [06-26]11:59:19.468 * block reached canonical chain*
INFO [06-26]11:59:19.468 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:59:19.468 Commit new sealing work
INFO [06-26]11:59:19.463 Successfully sealed new block
INFO [06-26]11:59:19.269 * mined potential block*
WARN [06-26]11:59:19.716 Snapshot extension registration failed
INFO [06-26]11:59:22.869 Looking for peers
number=139,296 sealhash=311586..e37639 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=4.640ms
number=139,295 sealhash=2b482c..f4f69c hash=66c925..4ca547 elapsed=7.338s
peer=44da81c9 err="peer connected on snap without compatible eth support"
peercount=0 tried=166 static=0
number=139,296 sealhash=311586..e37639 hash=bf9bc8..f4b915 elapsed=0.780s
number=139,299 sealhash=4d4cd0..f16809
number=139,296 hash=bf9bc8..f4b915
number=139,297 sealhash=3a66a0..f10f92 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=1.060ms
number=139,297 sealhash=3a66a0..f10f92 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=1.714ms
number=139,297 sealhash=3a66a0..f10f92 hash=b52196..13a115 elapsed=752.637ms
number=139,290 hash=b179f1..c490d9
number=139,297 hash=b52196..13a115
number=139,298 sealhash=2b762c..90e8d6 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=736.305µs
number=139,298 sealhash=2b762c..90e8d6 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=1.318ms
peer=03cb74f err="peer connected on snap without compatible eth support"
number=139,298 sealhash=2b762c..90e8d6 hash=5ea43d..b3df44 elapsed=4.269s
number=139,291 hash=88a217..9661bc
number=139,298 hash=5ea43d..b3df44
number=139,299 sealhash=37b5a0..1f1024 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=1.773ms
number=139,299 sealhash=37b5a0..1f1024 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=4.113ms
number=139,299 sealhash=37b5a0..1f1024 hash=7a8669..573bac elapsed=5.533s
number=139,292 hash=8cf025..cadd7f
number=139,300 sealhash=21a302..b8338b uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=5.740ms
number=139,300 sealhash=21a302..b8338b uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=7.738ms
number=139,299 sealhash=21a302..b8338b hash=716572..11057f elapsed=3.886s
number=139,293 hash=9367ad..5bc800
number=139,300 hash=716572..11057f
number=139,301 sealhash=2d4bf2..bb6436 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=11.749ms
number=139,301 sealhash=2d4bf2..bb6436 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=54.859ms
number=139,301 sealhash=2d4bf2..bb6436 hash=9cd08c..a328f2 elapsed=6.994s
number=139,294 hash=55f724..c8ba30
number=139,301 hash=9cd08c..a328f2
number=139,302 sealhash=2b8301..f73ba0 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=2.025ms
number=139,302 sealhash=2b8301..f73ba0 hash=64397e..9be622 elapsed=10.286ms
number=139,302 sealhash=2b8301..f73ba0 hash=64397e..9be622 elapsed=1.719s
number=139,295 hash=66c925..4ca547
number=139,302 hash=64397e..9be622
number=139,303 sealhash=78c539..b77fae uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=671.045µs
number=139,303 sealhash=78c539..b77fae uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=1.232ms
peercount=0 tried=128 static=0
peercount=1 tried=203 static=0
number=139,297 sealhash=78c539..b77fae hash=afdcf7..104509 elapsed=20.141s
number=139,296 hash=bf9bc8..f4b915
number=139,303 hash=afdcf7..104509
number=139,304 sealhash=adf835..3168f0 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=3.462ms
number=139,304 sealhash=adf835..3168f0 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=4.838ms
peercount=1 tried=129 static=0
number=139,304 sealhash=adf835..3168f0 hash=03ac46..396afc elapsed=15.391s
number=139,297 hash=b52196..13a115
number=139,305 sealhash=5235e5..e4ca2f uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=12.118ms
number=139,305 sealhash=5235e5..e4ca2f uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=13.028ms
peercount=1 tried=83 static=0
number=139,305 sealhash=5235e5..e4ca2f hash=627b11..17b3f2 elapsed=6.012s
number=139,298 hash=5ea43d..b3df44
number=139,305 hash=627b11..17b3f2
number=139,306 sealhash=bd5537..dbbcf3 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=963.188µs
number=139,306 sealhash=bd5537..dbbcf3 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=1.830ms
number=139,307 sealhash=bd5537..dbbcf3 hash=b5b526..829b44 elapsed=2.699s
number=139,299 hash=7a8669..573bac
number=139,307 sealhash=bd5537..dbbcf3 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=85.497ms
number=139,307 sealhash=bd5537..dbbcf3 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=86.650ms
number=139,306 hash=b5b526..829b44
peercount=2 tried=167 static=0
number=139,308 sealhash=716572..11057f
number=139,308 sealhash=725f66..725322 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=1.163ms
number=139,308 sealhash=725f66..725322 uncles=0 txs=0 gas=0 fees=0 elapsed=3.010ms
number=139,307 sealhash=8155f2..a155f2 hash=b0e981..07dea7 elapsed=9.277s
number=139,307 hash=80e981..07dea7
peer=0cae2994 err="peer connected on snap without compatible eth support"
peercount=0 tried=122 static=0

```

Figure 16 - Transactions SIGRUN BLC 2

11.3. Harmonization Opportunities

11.3.1. WP4 harmonization opportunities

11.3.1.1. CO.WP4.15. Location of near/nearest vehicles

Locating vehicles and tracking them is becoming a core function for an intelligent vehicle fleet system. GNSS (e.g., Galileo or GPS) provides the tools for such a vehicle fleet tracking system allowing managers to know in real time the vehicle position and select which can, in the shortest time, respond to a victim's request. A relevant problem that can arise in a collaboration scenario between emergency services is the difficulty in being effective by coordinating their fleet of vehicles and mobile assets to manage the incident.

The fleet management systems of the different agencies that are going to intervene jointly in a disaster can work in cooperation for which a standard for vehicles sharing position/location was included in the functions of VALKYRIES.

The SIGRUN framework provides such mechanisms to register and share the vehicles' location and status of all the joint forces entities. Any MCI response entity can make available their assets for the joint force, by registering its assets in the SIGRUN at any time and remove it or make it unavailable at any time. Their status is updated to the SIGRUN, and any Federated tools are updated with the register vehicles status and position in real-time.

On the other hand, vehicles location functions support I) the responsible for dispatching the victims to the destination to assign a vehicle (ambulance or transport) based on its status and the faster to reach the victim or the faster to transport the victim to the medical service assigned; II) allows the destination service to track the MCI victims transport vehicle position and have a more precise time of the victim arrival (ETA).

The result is better management of the dispatching services and better preparedness of the medical services to respond to MCI events.

The tests aim to validate the correct report of the victims' and assets position, their updating time and time elapsed between its report and being displayed in the GLOBL COP.

11.3.1.2. CO.WP4.28. Cross Border Data Trace

Enhance the synchronization of actions/decision-making due to the same knowledge of tactical and on-field conditions on the catastrophic event, the victim's location/status, and alerts-warnings. [1]

Through sharing the COP created by the SIGRUN system architecture, you linked heterogeneous federated systems (with non-compatible to each other own COPs) when exchanging the minimum data set of information according to SIGRUN specs and standards introduced. [1]

11.3.1.3. CO.WP4.42. Reduce Voice communication, digitalizing most information exchanges

Reducing the number of voice calls in disaster management can significantly impact the effectiveness of emergency response and the ability of response teams to use their resources more efficiently. It's essential for several reasons: resources are limited. They must be used efficiently and for critical tasks, agility in emergency management (voice calls can be a slow communication) and increased accuracy and efficiency in decision-making (voice calls can be prone to errors and misunderstanding). [1]

There are several ways to reduce the number of voice calls in emergency and disaster management: using mobile applications allows users to send information in real-time and receive updates in real-time, automating processes to reduce workload ante the time required to complete a task (for example, automating patient registration), using technologies for real-time collaboration and instant updating of information and using unifies communications technologies. [1]

11.3.1.4. CO.WP4.55. Use of wearables to support triage

In the framework of the Valkyries project, the different information communication processes for each UC have been analysed and a Command and Control tool has been used to automate and centralise the information related to the incident. On the other hand, this tool has been integrated into the SIGRUN reference model, which has allowed all the applications to share information in an agile way, avoiding analogue communications and preventing information from being distributed inappropriately

To create a new standard in triage / non triage supportive applications on victims that need / do not need hospitalization and for tracking geolocation / vital signs / status data of first responders and their vehicles / supportive equipment. [1]

Use NFC (or other tagging passive technologies) or a pre-established QR/Bar code marked on the bracelets, within wearables (e.g., coloured bracelets) linking data related with victims' registration and follow up in Blockchain networks, as per the SIGRUN overall architecture. [1]

11.3.1.5. CO.WP4.21. Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

The storage of data related to emergency situations, such as fires, earthquakes and other natural or man-made disasters, represents an invaluable resource for improving preparedness and response to similar events in the future. This data recording and analysis, within the framework of emergency data management or crisis data management, has multiple benefits.

First, it allows learning from past experiences, which is essential to understand how emergencies evolved and how they were handled. This provides critical information for response teams and authorities to improve their strategies and protocols. In addition, data warehousing facilitates the optimization of resources during an emergency by identifying patterns and trends in past incidents, which means that resources can be allocated more efficiently, deployed where they are most needed and when they are needed.

Stored information is also essential for long-term strategic planning. Authorities and response organizations can use this data to develop more effective emergency plans and stronger prevention policies.

In emergency situations, informed decision-making is crucial. Stored data allows leaders to evaluate similar situations from the past and apply lessons learned to make better decisions in real time.

Coordination between different agencies and organizations involved in emergency response benefits from stored data, as it facilitates the sharing of accurate and timely information.

In addition, this data has significant value in the field of technology and artificial intelligence, particularly in the training of Machine Learning algorithms. Historical data from emergency situations is used to train Machine Learning models capable of predicting the occurrence of similar events in the future. This improves anticipation and response capabilities, which can save lives and reduce the impact of emergencies.

In addition, recorded data is essential for assessing the long-term impact on infrastructure, the economy and the wider community, which is critical for effective recovery and reconstruction.

These data are also used in scientific research and technology development, helping to better understand natural phenomena and to develop more advanced emergency detection and prediction technologies.

The same strategy has been used in the different UCs for the generation and storage of these data as well as for the extraction, processing and training of these data:

1. SIGRUN: This is the central part of the whole system, this platform links all the data collected by the different sources present in the simulations and stores them in a database.
2. Extraction: After the exercise has taken place, an extraction of the data from the database is carried out to document it.
3. Processing and training: The extracted data is collected and transformed into a more user-friendly format for cleaning, normalization and transformation. Finally, this data is

used for training of disantos Machine Learning models to optimize processes and thus improve our system and the procedures of the first responders.

11.3.1.6. CO.WP4.2. Logistics assistance using UAV's

UAVs can provide a variety of tasks. For a disaster relief mission, searching for areas for casualties and building situational awareness will reduce the time for C2 to get a clear picture. They can be relay on platforms making communication and coordination of the assists easier, and they can deliver parcels of necessary equipment or medicines to first responders or casualties. This work will decrease the need for people to do logistics, relieving them of first response work, and it will speed up the process of assisting casualties and getting the disaster under control. [1]

By deploying UAVs in autonomous search patterns and using swarm theory. UAVs can give the almost continuous cover of the area to give situation awareness and communications opportunities for the first responders and C2. A common data platform like SIGRUN will provide everyone involved with the same information and the possibility to get essential equipment by UAV delivery systems. Machine learning will improve the system's ability to deliver the optimum service. [1]

11.3.2. WP5 harmonization opportunities

The VALKYRIES Use Cases (UC) present to the target audience the results of the VALKYRIES Project's certification, regulation, standardisation and harmonisation activities, including those related to WP5, as well as the improvement potential arising from the combination of solutions on the SIGRUN platform.

In relation to the opportunities and enablers proposed in WP5, a number of selected procedures and solutions were harmonised and applied in the context of the cross-border disaster developed in UC3, and the results were evaluated.

The assessment of the enablers in the UC demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:

- Questionnaires in the framework of the specific training actions of the UC: Within the development days of the UC, training and coaching sessions were carried out in relation to the operating procedures using the the enablers proposed by VALKYRIES (for example TASSICA 3 triage cards or some federated tools through SIGRUN used in the simulations). In these sessions, the participants practised all the steps and roles involved in the different specific operating procedures proposed for attending to victims of a MCI or disaster. At the end of these actions, the responders answered a questionnaire to collect their assessment.
- Records made during the exercise: Collection of the information necessary to evaluate the MEs (mission success measures) and to determine whether or not the established KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) were met. These records were made
 - Manually: for those exercises developed outside the SIGRUN federated system, through a network of VALKYRIES' own evaluators.
 - Automatically: for those exercises developed using the SIGRUN federated system, from the data stored in it.
- On-line questionnaires at the end of the UC to collect the evaluation of the participants in the simulation.

Details on the methodology and design of the demonstrations carried out can be found in Deliverable D7.3.

11.3.2.1. *CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response*

CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response: CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for the response planning, preparedness and execution of Project UCs.

Standardized terminology in emergency and disaster planning at the EU level is essential for clear, consistent communication and increased efficiency. The VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and implementation (VALKYRIES GLOSSARY) is a web-based, multilingual database of technical terms related to emergencies, designed to improve planning, communication, and coordination among first responders. This glossary, developed within the VALKYRIES project, is a prototype, aligned with deliverable D5.4 guidelines, and serves as a limited-scope example to test its effectiveness. It seeks to provide a unified understanding of terms for VALKYRIES researchers.

11.3.2.2. *CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans*

For effective coordination in emergency response planning, information must be standardised, structured, securely shared and readily available when needed. The STRUCTURED REPOSITORY OF EU EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS (EUR-ERP) aims to provide decision-makers with the information needed to coordinate cross-border disaster responses within the European Union Civil Protection system. Within the VALKYRIES project, the EUR-ERP is a prototype, which follows the guidelines of deliverable D5.4. It aims to provide VALKYRIES use cases with the necessary information to coordinate emergency plans in the territories involved

11.3.2.3. *CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response*

CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response: Two enablers have been evaluated to the UC demonstrator to address this opportunity:

- CO.WP5-7-1 Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: Use of unified casualties triage priority coding (VALKYRIES pentapolar coding) and tagging (colours) in the UC. The VALKYRIES project proposes to establish an EU-wide standardised code to unify the coding and labelling of casualties in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters, based primarily on NATO standards. It is proposed to implement a pentapolar triage coding with the following triage priorities and colours for casualty tagging: PT 1 IMMEDIATE (Red), PT2 DELAYED (Yellow), PT3 MINIMAL (Green), PT4 EXPECTANT (Blue), D DECEASED (Black).
- CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: Use and evaluation of the TASSICA 3 triage card in the UC. VALKYRIES proposes the use of a standardised triage card (TASSICA 3) in the EU for the recording of key casualty information by the different emergency services that may intervene in a MCI. To this end, based on this enabler (TASSICA 3 triage card), a review and homogenisation of the following operational procedures of each service involved in the UC was carried out:
 - Primary triage

- Application of immediate life-saving measures
- Stabilisation of the victims
- Secondary triage
- Evacuation
- Recording of casualties clinical information
- Communications

11.3.2.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response: Use of the Emergency Medical Services Minimum Data Set (EMS MDS) as the standard for information exchange in UCs demonstrators.

When responding to mass casualty incidents (MCI) or disasters, it's essential to exchange information between the various services to coordinate the response effectively. Yet, emergency services often gather data that isn't uniformly relevant or standardized, posing a challenge to smooth integration.

Standardisation of information is a prerequisite for any exchange of information, regardless of whether it is data, voice or any other form. It is therefore necessary to move in this direction in order to facilitate the exchange of information between different first responders or civil protection authorities within a country or between countries in cross-border disasters.

VALKYRIES proposes a Minimum Data Set (EMS MDS) for Emergency Medical Services to share during MCIs and disasters concerning victim care. This EMS MDS includes data such as victim identification, characteristics, contact details, location, injuries, clinical updates, and other vital information.

11.3.2.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response: Deployment and evaluation of SIGRUN as an integration reference to facilitate the deployment and response of emergency services in the UC demonstrator.

In order to support adequate information sharing for an effective response to an MCI or disaster, a federated system of applications operated by different emergency services, as well as different external data sources, could provide a solid basis for harmonisation and standardisation of IT systems, workflows and other issues that have been identified as major barriers to system interoperability, whether within a single country or in major cross-border disasters.

SIGRUN is the VALKYRIES common framework used to federate a set of interrelated technology solutions to support first responder C2, logistics, deployment and medical care procedures and improve shared situational awareness in response to a multi-casualty incident or disaster.

The VALKYRIES project proposes to use SIGRUN to federate a set of interlinked capabilities of different emergency services to support the response to a multi-casualty incident or disaster at different levels:

- Sharing information about the incident and casualties between first responders at the scene, promoting interoperability and making their work more effective (deployment, logistics, search and rescue, triage, stabilisation, evacuation).

- Sharing information between pre-hospital and hospital facilities to ensure continuity of medical care for victims.
- Improving situational awareness and support C2 decision making through a common COP.

To this end, based on this enabler (SIGRUN federated system), a review and homogenisation of the following operational procedures of each service involved in the UC was carried out:

- Incident reporting
- Search & Rescue
- Primary triage
- Application of immediate life-saving measures
- Stabilisation of the victims
- Secondary triage
- Evacuation

11.3.2.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response: Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the UC.

The initial shared information on the characteristics of the incident during an MCI or disaster is critical to initiating and maintaining an effective emergency response. By standardising early warning procedures for such incidents, stakeholders can be assured that they will receive consistent and understandable details about the situation or threat and the appropriate steps to address it.

VALKYRIES researchers support the METHANE model (proposed in the UK by JESIP in its "Joint Doctrine: the interoperability framework") as incident-related Minimum Data Set (MDS) to provide a common structure for responders and their control centres to share incident information in a consistent, rapid and simple manner.

11.3.3. WP6 harmonization opportunities

11.3.3.1. CO.WP6.2. Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

The use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data in emergency situations, such as fires, earthquakes and other natural or man-made disasters, represents a critical advance in crisis data management and the preservation of information security.

First, cryptography provides an additional layer of security for stored emergency-related data. This ensures that critical information, such as details of response operations, contingency plans and personal data, is kept confidential and protected from unauthorised access, even in chaotic situations.

In addition, the application of cryptographic mechanisms ensures data integrity. This means that stored data cannot be altered or manipulated by unauthorised persons, which is essential to maintain the accuracy and reliability of information during an emergency.

Cryptography also plays a key role in the authentication of data and users. In emergency situations, authentication ensures that only authorised parties have access to critical

information. This prevents the spread of erroneous or malicious information that could hamper response operations.

Data protection through cryptography is essential not only during an emergency, but also in the long-term storage phase. As historical data accumulates, it is vital to ensure its continued security to maintain information integrity and comply with privacy regulations.

To realise this opportunity, the same has been done in the various use cases. To protect the data being exchanged between the different data sources with SIGRUN, the HTTPS protocol has been implemented, which is capable of encrypting the information sent over the network, making it invisible to anyone. In this way, the privacy and confidentiality of the data is achieved.

11.3.3.2. CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

Virtual Operation Support Teams are support units in disaster management that can generate additional information for crisis teams, decision-makers (Incident Commanders). The impact of this opportunity is that VOSTs can also be supportive and assist the authority in communicating through its own network. Those teams are networked within Europe (in some countries) and worldwide. This opportunity does not mean creation of VOSTs, but the use, support and exploitation of VOSTs.

11.3.3.3. CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.

This opportunity proposes definition of a minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers for their successful integration in the operational procedures and to reach adequate volunteers' protection with risk-free activities. The aid of volunteers in case of MCI is fundamental but it is also very important that volunteers are always safe and useful for professional first aid teams. At the EU level, there are no existing specific training courses. The proposal is therefore to create a definition of a minimum set of competencies and skills to be acquired to be an effective and safe in case of cross-border MCI.

11.3.3.4. CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions can improve the joint multinational civil-military training of various representatives engaged in actions in the defeat zone and emergency situations. This will help them use joint military capabilities to perform activities at various cross-border MCIs. This opportunity covers a creation of curriculum, methodology and guidance with procedures, steps and technics for joint multinational civil-military training in the case of emergencies.

11.3.3.5. CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).

This opportunity proposes the standardization of education and training for first aid responses (training kit: curriculum, training methodology and training manual). This training kit will build on some existing training materials used by first aid responders in the Bulgarian Military Medical Academy and the VALKYRIES partners. By implementing this opportunity will be improved Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training of different groups of First Responders who acquire basic knowledge and practical skills for performing life-saving activities in various types of trauma and medical conditions in case of cross-border MCI.